

D2.2

DAFNE+ Use-case specifications

Revision v1.0

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the specification of the DAFNE+ use-cases at the end of the first year of the project and the methodology and concepts that were developed to produce it. The specification results from a process that involved the use-cases partners including feedback from the targeted communities. It structures each the 3 main use-cases into scenarios related to specific user roles and managed assets and proposes a synthesis of preliminary research outcomes on governance and monetization aspects. Its main motivation being to prepare the launch of the use-case pilots, it also presents the use-case implementation strategy structured into 3 main action lines – promotion, user support and community management, evaluation - to be carried out at the various levels of the use-cases organization.

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Use-case, user feedback, blockchain, NFT, DAO, art, culture, heritage, sound, music, maker, design, open source

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary	8
2	Introduction	9
2.1	Purpose and context of the document	9
2.2	Document structure	9
2.3	Dependencies to-from other WPs	9
3	Use-cases specification process and concepts	10
3.1	Storylines – internal consortium elaboration	10
3.2	Scenarios resulting from user feedback	10
3.3	Governance and monetization aspects	11
3.4	Use-cases implementation strategy	11
4	Use-case scenarios	12
4.1	Use-case 1 - User generated content at large for heritage	12
4.1.1	Summary	12
4.1.2	Background to Use-case 1 scenarios	12
4.1.3	Key findings from the user feedback process	14
4.1.4	Targeted users, assets, and usage	14
4.1.5	DAO related rules	16
4.1.6	Scenario 1.1 - Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage	16
4.1.7	Scenario 1.2 - Students from MMU School of Digital Arts	17
4.2	Use-case 2 - Experimental sound/music production	20
4.2.1	Summary	20
4.2.2	Background to Use-case 2 scenarios	20
4.2.3	Key findings from the user-feedback process	22
4.2.4	Targeted users, assets, and usage	24
4.2.5	DAO related rules	26
4.2.6	Scenario 2.1 – Creation and use of components	26
4.2.7	Scenario 2.2 – Creation and use of work repositories	28

4.2.8	Scenario 2.3 – Creation and use of works / private spaces.....	31
4.3	Use-case 3 - Novel forms of artistic content exploitation	33
4.3.1	Summary	33
4.3.2	Background to Use-case 3 scenarios.....	33
4.3.3	Key findings from the user feedback process.....	34
4.3.4	Targeted users, assets, and usage.....	36
4.3.5	DAO related rules.....	36
4.3.6	Scenario 3.1 - Repository/Component creator.....	36
4.3.7	Scenario 3.2 – Repository/Component user.....	38
4.3.8	Scenario 3.3 - Repository/Component contributor.....	39
5	Governance and monetization framework.....	41
5.1	Governance framework.....	41
5.1.1	Chat.....	41
5.1.2	Forum.....	41
5.1.3	Proposals and voting.....	41
5.2	Monetization framework.....	42
5.2.1	NFT Marketplace.....	42
5.2.2	Redistribution and Fees.....	42
5.2.3	DAO Funds: Grants, Prices, Community Initiatives, Proposals	42
5.3	Initial economic and governance models	42
5.3.1	Self-declaration of contributions for revenue sharing.....	43
5.3.2	Progressive platform fees	43
5.3.3	Democratic platform governance.....	43
5.3.4	Collective fund management	43
6	Use-case implementation strategy	44
6.1	Promotion.....	44
6.1.1	Value proposals and punchlines	44
6.1.2	At Project level (UPM)	46
6.1.3	Use-case 1	47
6.1.4	Use-case 2	47
6.1.5	Use-case 3	48

6.2	User support and community management.....	50
6.2.1	At Project level.....	50
6.2.2	Use-case 1	50
6.2.3	Use-case 2	51
6.2.4	Use-case 3	51
6.3	Monitoring and evaluation.....	51
6.3.1	Introduction	51
6.3.2	Means of evaluation.....	52
6.3.3	Methodology and timeline.....	52
6.3.4	Use Case Metrics.....	56
7	Conclusions	61

List of tables

Table 1 KPIs from the GA that will be assessed in the pilots and the relevant means for producing them.....	54
Table 2 Questionnaire to be used in the pilots with the end users.....	55
Table 3 Questionnaire to be used in the pilots with the experts.....	56
Table 4 Problem relevance metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them.....	57
Table 5 Solution relevance metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them.....	58
Table 6 Solution performance metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them.....	59
Table 7 Usability metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them.....	59
Table 8 Motivation and engagement metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them.....	60

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content Management System
CNC milling	Computer Numerical Control milling
DAO	Distributed Autonomous Organization
DRM	Digital Right Management system
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NFT	Non Fungible Token
NWFA	North West Film Archive
RAVE	Real-time Audio Variational autoEncoder
STMS	Science and Technology of Music and Sound
UGC	User Generated Content
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WYSIWYG	What You See Is What You Get – an expected feature of graphical interfaces
XR	Extended Reality

1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the specification of the DAFNE+ use-cases at the end of the first year of the project and the methodology and concepts that were developed to produce it. The specification results from a process that involved the use-cases partners through successive stages including feedback from the targeted communities. It structures each of the 3 main use-cases into scenarios related to specific user roles and managed assets and proposes a synthesis of preliminary research outcomes on governance and monetization aspects. Its main motivation being to prepare the launch of the use-case pilots, it also presents the use-case implementation strategy structured into 3 main action lines – promotion, user support and community management, evaluation - to be carried out at the various levels of the use-cases organization.

An updated version of the specifications is to be produced at M24 as a result of the evaluation of the first phase of the use-case pilots.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and context of the document

This deliverable presents the activities and results of Task 2.3 during the first year of the project. More specifically, Task 2.3 was devoted to the refined specification of DAFNE+ use cases, following the co-creation and user feedback activities carried out as part of Task 2.1. The specification is formalized in several scenarios within the framework of each use-case; it also includes a synthesis of the governance and monetization framework applicable to all use-cases, resulting from preliminary outcomes of WP6. Finally, it proposes a presentation of the use-case implementation strategy at the very start of WP5, which will serve as an initial definition for the actions to be carried out as part of the use-case pilots.

2.2 Document structure

The rest of this document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 3 describes the process and resulting concepts of task 2.3.
- Chapter 4 presents the detailed use-case specification based on user-scenarios.
- Chapter 5 proposes a synthesis of the governance and monetization framework applicable to use-cases.
- Chapter 6 exposes the use-case implementation strategy.
- Chapter 7 concludes this deliverable.

2.3 Dependencies to-from other WPs

This deliverable depends on:

- WP6 for the governance and monetization framework applicable to all use-cases.
- WP7 for the strategy of promotion, user support and community management.

It provides valuable information to:

- WP3 for the evaluation framework of the tools
- WP4 for additional qualitative feedback on the use-cases
- WP5 for the specification of the use-case pilots implementation
- WP6 for use-case feedbacks on legal, governance and monetization aspects
- WP7 for the strategy of dissemination, user support and community management for each use-case community

3 Use-cases specification process and concepts

The starting point for the definition of the use-cases was their presentation in the GA. It distinguishes 3 main use-cases, each targeting various creative communities through the management of specific assets in the blockchain/NFT platform, that also structure the organization of WP5:

1. User generated content at large for heritage (lead: UPM)
2. Experimental music production (lead: IRCAM)
3. Novel forms of artistic content exploitation (lead: IAAC)

The use-case specification presented in this document is an outcome of task T2.3, but it was initiated as part of task T2.1 which carried out the user feedback process and fed both the technical specification as part of T2.2 and the refined use-case specifications as part of T2.3. The process related to T2.1 is presented in deliverable D2.1.

The successive stages of use-case specification and conceptual elaboration are summarized in the next paragraphs.

3.1 Storylines – internal consortium elaboration

In the framework of task T2.1, several workshops gathered the whole consortium to exchange on the different use-cases through a common analysis grid based on *storylines* identifying managed assets, user types and roles and their potential interests for each storyline. This process enabled to identify aspects specific or common to several use-cases. In particular, although very different on the addressed communities and types of digital contents managed, a lot of similarity emerged on the main categories of assets to be managed and user roles in relation to these categories. A common vocabulary was adopted and converged on the concepts of *Components* and *Repositories*. *Components* are technical modules (code scripts, libraries, executables, databases...) that intervene in digital creative tools, whereas *Repositories* gather technical elements including components for a creative process. The distinction between them lies less on their technical form than on their purpose: Components are produced by technical experts and perform a generic technical process independently of a specific artistic project, whereas Repositories are the support of a creative process, in particular for the production or reproduction of the artifact. Another important dimension resulting from the exchange on storylines was the collective dimension of the creative processes in relation to the managed assets, with different roles assigned to various categories of users.

3.2 Scenarios resulting from user feedback

This stage of definition of use-cases by the DAFNE+ consortium was then confronted to the user feedback process combining answers to the survey, workshops and interviews managed by the use-case partners. It brought very informative feedback and new ideas that contributed to update the use-case specification. What emerged then was the necessity of structuring each use-case in several scenarios, involving different assets and/or user communities and roles. This division also enabled to clarify the respective responsibilities of use-case partners on scenarios, with one main partner per scenario. For each scenario, one or several user journeys define the succession of stages involving the various stakeholders. Moreover, the presentation of each use-case scenario includes relevant expectations if any on DAO related rules.

The resulting structure of use-cases/scenarios is the following:

1. User generated content at large for heritage (lead: UPM)
 - 1.1. Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage (UPM)
 - 1.2. Students from MMU School of Digital Arts (SODA)

2. Experimental sound/music production (lead: IRCAM)
 - 2.1. Creation and use of components (IRCAM)
 - 2.2. Creation and use of work repositories (IRCAM)
 - 2.3. Creation and use of works / private spaces (IRCAM)
3. Novel forms of artistic content exploitation (lead: IAAC)
 - 3.1. Repository/Component creator (IAAC)
 - 3.2. Repository/Component user (IAAC)
 - 3.3. Repository/Component contributor (IAAC)

The structure of presentation for the specification of each use-case is the following:

Use-case X:

- Summary
- Background to Use-case scenarios: *presentation of Use-case X existing context*
- Key findings from the user feedback process: *synthesis of the qualitative aspects of user feedback applicable to all Use-case X scenarios*
- Targeted users, assets and usage: *presentation of the key aspects of Use-case X*
- DAO related rules : *expectations on DAO rules at Use-case level*
- Description of Scenarios X.Y:
 - Scenario description
 - User profiles
 - Managed assets
 - Promotional materials: *elements needed to present the assets in the marketplace*
 - Presentation of user journeys: *succession of stages involving the various stakeholders*

3.3 Governance and monetization aspects

Although not organized as part of T2.3 but WP6 and WP4, it appeared relevant in the framework of the use-case specification to include a synthesis of the current work hypotheses of the research and innovation activities conducted on governance and monetization aspects that are an integral part of the use-cases.

3.4 Use-cases implementation strategy

In addition to specifying the use cases from a functional point of view for the target users, it was important in T2.3 to also draw up the implementation strategy from the point of view of the consortium partners involved in the use cases, in order to prepare the work for WP5.

Following the organization of use-case pilots in WP5 in one task per use-case (T5.1 to T5.3) and one task for evaluation (T5.4), 3 main actions lines have been identified as part of WP5 as successive stages of users involvement:

1. Promotion: *incentivization of targeted users to join the platform.*
2. User support and community management: *support and animation of the community of registered users.*
3. Evaluation: *monitoring and analysis of the platform usage on relevant indicators.*

These objectives cross those of WP7 for Actions lines 1&2 (dissemination) and WP6&7 (research on business aspects, impact assessment) for Action line 3.

Consequently, a coordination framework is planned between the relevant project partners to divide the work for each line of action between actions at the overall Project level and actions at the Use-case or Scenario levels, more focused on specific communities, according to the following use case structure:

The action plan as of the date of production of this document, i.e. at the start of WP5 is presented in the use-case implementation strategy in Part 6 at the Project and Scenario levels. It is to be considered as a first basis that shall evolve over time.

4 Use-case scenarios

4.1 Use-case 1 - User generated content at large for heritage

4.1.1 Summary

The User Generated Content (UGC) – content created by prosumers - is a field where heritage content can benefit from the sharing and participation in DAOs. Prosumers who create content in the cultural heritage sector include professional, student and amateur subject specialists as well as users who wish to share an emotional response or reminiscence about an object or topic, even users who can contribute factual information or corrections about particular objects can be included as part of the Use Case 1 community. The kind of content can be images, photos, or fiction in response to cultural heritage content.

This use case is divided in two main scenarios:

Scenario 1.1 : Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage (UPM)

DAFNE+ platform provides a decentralized and autonomous ecosystem for the creation, discovery, and distribution of cultural heritage content. This ecosystem empowers users to have control over their content and the distribution of revenues, fostering collaboration and participation among communities of users. The use of DAOs ensures that users have a say in the platform's operations and that the platform is governed in a transparent and fair manner, aligning with the users' vision of a decentralized and autonomous platform.

Scenario 1.2: Students from MMU School of Digital Arts (SODA)

SODA creative media student working as part of team must produce artwork using North West Film Archive (NWFA)* and/or other footage from MMU's NFT Shareloom student and staff, for community arts events organised as part of DAFNE+ testing – a gallery exhibition.

4.1.2 Background to Use-case 1 scenarios

4.1.2.1 Scenario 1.1: Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage

The Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) is a well-known institution with a strong background in research and innovation, particularly in media and cultural heritage. UPM's vast expertise and multidisciplinary approach will lead the user-generated content use case within the DAFNE+ platform.

UPM is a leader in media-related research. Its research centers, faculties, and academic programs offer a deep understanding of media creation, distribution, and consumption processes, enabling UPM to address the challenges and opportunities associated with user-generated content.

UPM values cultural heritage and its preservation, recognizing the importance of user-generated content in fostering engagement and participation. UPM's commitment to empowering content creators aligns with the objectives of the use case, as it seeks to provide a platform where users can contribute their unique perspectives, experiences, and creations.

4.1.2.2 Scenario 1.2: Students from MMU School of Digital Arts

Users in Scenario 1.2 are students at Manchester Metropolitan University's School of Digital Arts (SODA).

SODA is a £35M investment into the workspaces, networks, teaching and research designed to drive the next generation of creative content. Production spaces in the school include dedicated virtual production, film and photography, UX testing, XR development and sound and music studios. SODA is ideally placed in a city that has transformed to be a leading powerhouse of the UK's digital economy, widely recognised as a national and international media hub, home to MediaCityUK, UK broadcasters the BBC and ITV, as well as a thriving creative and cultural scene.

Students in the school are involved in the many collaborative units that emphasize the importance of collaboration and experimentation in the digital and creative sector. They compose work with a wide range of media: video (film and animation), 3D games engine-based media, sound and music, XR and other interactive experiences on a range of topics including local heritage. Student users of DAFNE+ need to be able to create work as part of a group working on a project, without diluting or confusing their claim to specific aspects of creative development. In addition, students would also be able to share more widely their work as an asset in the growing student NFT art network MMU Shareloom. MMU Shareloom will integrate with DAFNE+ by facilitating a creative community hub that includes MMU creative students and partner organisations, which shares, records and exchanges creative assets. A key use case scenario will be the preparation of creative work for student shows that use heritage footage from a partner organisation, (for example, the North West Film Archive – see below).

MMU Shareloom is an online community curating a growing media collection that comprises SODA student content shared by students and collectors, as well as assets by key content providers such as NWFA and other SODA media partners on the basis of strong blockchain DRM (such as DAFNE+ smart contracts). Based on research, content owners in the use case could give permission for their content to be used based on a three (or more) tier system of rights:

- permission to view.
- permission to use non-commercially/for educational purposes.
- permission to use commercially.

Users will access the collection through a subsection/tag/category of the DAFNE+ system using search and AI content management facilities to categorize and make discoverable new and relevant content. A token-based system (or similar) will give them access to the content based on one or more of the pre-agreed tiers. Many elements of community management will occur on the chat social media application Discord, allowing it to integrate with DAFNE+ on core aspects of community management and tool functionality offered by the platform.

4.1.3 Key findings from the user feedback process

SODA students, staff and two external partners were surveyed as part of the user requirements gathering for DAFNE+. The following elements reflect findings from the user feedback process:

- Whilst most understood the landscape of blockchain and NFT fairly well there was a general lack of adoption of blockchain technologies, by both SODA staff, external partners and students. Very few participants owned an NFT wallet, for example – DAFNE+ should add basic information and a means of blockchain or NFT adoption into the user journey – this seamless approach will lower barrier to entry, key to adoption and sustained usage.
- Little evidence of existing plans to use blockchain in platforms (BBC & NWFA) but some interest. The DAFNE+ platform can provide new and unique services to external partners but a lightweight model of interaction with the API which requires less development by partner organisations to integrate may be preferable at this stage.
- Good evidence of a need to protect content producers/owners from theft and cultivate trust between these actors and mainstream platforms - a core concern for users. This included being protected from ML corpus content 'scraping' activity (the latter is perhaps an edge case).
- Simplification of rights management and user interface was also highlighted as a priority. The spectre of blockchain currently conjures fears of techno-elitism and unnecessary complexity that does not always chime well with digital creatives.
- Wide range of media types used with very different outputs to both mainstream and bespoke platforms – use case addresses different ways to use DAFNE+ different media types.
- Importance of both digital and analogue collaborations and creative practices, especially via events.
- Conversations with BBC Makerbox in particular highlighted the challenges of developing sustainable and active communities around new creative technologies and platforms. Repeated online and in-venue events aligned to existing activity and organisations is key. Whilst this is not only a technical consideration it highlights the need for flexibility, low-barrier to entry to access the benefits of the platform and a reason to maintain engagement.
- Algorithmic automation tools (e.g. Midjourney, GPT-3) are considered by staff and students to be an important trend in digital culture but there is an ongoing criticality about developing ethical practices in this space.
- In terms of 3D assets, many students are already engaged with using industry-standard games engines and game art tools. Therefore, 3D asset generation should be aimed either at community/fun aspects of the platform or outputs should be easily shared via standard formats e.g. ABC, USD, OBJ, FBX, PLY, STL.

4.1.4 Targeted users, assets, and usage

Here we can find a list of the main users we will have in this use-case for both scenarios. Assets are described in the scenario sections.

4.1.4.1 Prosumers (Scenario 1.1)

- They are in their 30s.
- They are history enthusiastic.

- They are tech-savvy and comfortable with using various tools and platforms to showcase their work, including social media and online communities. They are always looking for new ways to reach a wider audience and monetize their work.
- Share content almost exclusively on social media channels: Instagram, Tik Tok, Vimeo, Youtube, Discord and Reddit.
- They don't have knowledge of blockchain and NFT technologies neither own a crypto wallet.
- Most of the work they currently produce is to show and preserve cultural heritage of their region. However, when they consider selling their work online through DAFNE+, the top three things they are concerned about are:
 - Recognition of their work.
 - Engagement with their communities.
 - Fair and transparent pricing and payment.

4.1.4.2 Content consumers (Scenario 1.1):

- They are in their mid-40s.
- They love traveling and learning about different cultures.
- They use internet and social media as primary source of information.
- They value high quality and accuracy of the information they consume.
- They know about decentralized platforms and have a notion on what an NFT is, but they don't own a crypto wallet.

4.1.4.3 SODA media student user persona (Scenario 1.2):

- 20-year-old Level 5 (second year undergraduate students)
- Study Future Media Production BA (undergraduate degree) where they are challenged to explore their ideas using a range of digital creation tools: Photoshop, After Effects, Premiere, Unreal Engine, Logic and Blender.
- Use AI automation tools to do initial designs and mockups for work.
- Share content almost exclusively on social media channels: Instagram, Tik Tok, Vimeo, Youtube, Discord and Reddit.
- They have some knowledge of blockchain and NFT technologies but do not currently own a crypto wallet.
- Most of the work they currently produce is for educational outputs. However, when they consider selling their work online through DAFNE+, the top three things they are concerned about are:
 - protection from theft.
 - ability to choose a suitable copyright agreement.
 - fair and transparent pricing and payment.

4.1.4.4 SODA secondary user summaries (Scenario 1.2):

- Lecturers: will be responsible for facilitating interactions with DAFNE+ and creating educational projects and public events that build a DAO community and forum based on SODA students, their networks, and audiences". They are currently interested in both DAFNE+ and blockchain technologies and a few are very involved in NFT culture, but most are not and are primarily critical of the NFT trend. They understand that DAFNE+ strives to be different to this.
- Content providers: *North West Film Archive (NWFA)*: provide content for students mainly as a bespoke service based on specific requirements. Most of the content is owned by thousands of private content owners and usage rights and terms vary as a result. They are interested in how they

might work to produce content for SODA students that uses blockchain technology in DAFNE+ to manage rights for students primarily and the general public secondarily.

- External audience and commissioners: these are members of the public that seek to purchase student work at shows, through online platforms or through commissions organised by the university.

4.1.5 DAO related rules

DAOs are organizations that operate on the blockchain and are governed by rules encoded as smart contracts. These rules ensure that all members of the DAO have a fair and known representation and decision-making power. This might allow for a more equitable distribution of resources, such as the revenues generated by the platform.

For content creators and artists, DAOs offer the opportunity to participate in a community of like-minded individuals and receive a fair share of the platform's revenues. They also give users the ability to make decisions about how the platform is run, from deciding on the rules for the distribution and use of content to the platform's overall operation.

In a DAO, users may hold governance tokens that represent their stake in the platform and give them the right to participate in decision-making processes. This interaction between users and the platform creates a sense of ownership and community, fostering collaboration and cooperation among users. Thus, DAFNE+ DAO should allow the users to:

- Make proposals on the operations of the platform.
- Make proposals on the operations and rules of the DAO.
- Vote on these proposals according to the rules of the DAO.
- Enforce the results of these proposals through smart contracts.

In Use Case 1.2, students and other staff may use the functionality of the DAO to also vote on certain creative opportunities, such as funding and prizes exclusive to the community for the purposes of growing a sustainable and engaged community that makes meaningful and impactful decisions.

4.1.6 Scenario 1.1 - Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage

4.1.6.1 Summary

Users, whether professionals or enthusiasts, can create and share content related to cultural heritage on DAFNE+ platform. Unlike traditional platforms controlled by external companies, DAFNE+ empowers users to have control over their content, decide how and where it is exchanged, and receive fair compensation for their contributions. Through decentralized autonomous organizations (DAOs), users can connect with like-minded individuals and communities, fostering collaboration and engagement. DAFNE+ aims to create a user-centric platform that values and rewards users' creativity and knowledge in the cultural heritage space.

4.1.6.2 Assets

- Digital images files e.g. .jpeg, .gif, .bmp, .tiff, .psd, .ai, .xcf, .png, .eps, etc...
- Digital video files e.g. .mp4, .mov, .wmv, .avi, .flv, .swf, .mkv, .ogg, etc...
- Digital audio files e.g. .aac, .mp3, .wav, .aiff, .pcm, .wma, .ogg, .flac, etc...
- Digital text files e.g. .txt, .doc, .html, .xls, .ltx, .json, .xml, etc...

4.1.6.3 Promotional materials

- Title.

- Author/s.
- Description.
- Media Type / Multiple Media Type.
- Snapshot.
- Traits, metadata of the characteristics and its rarity.
- If is part of a collection the link to the whole collection.

4.1.6.4 User Journeys

4.1.6.4.1 Prosumer

1. User logs into the platform and create or connect their wallet to interact with the assets of the platform.
2. Search into the platform to document herself into the topic she is going to produce content about.
3. If she likes the content, she looks to the license of the content and if available uses it for her new creation.
4. She writes a script of the content she is going to produce, that can be used as a blog post.
5. She goes to the place where the cultural event, historic building, or performance is and takes some photos and/or videos.
6. She edits the photos and/or videos if it is possible in the platform, so she can add the copyright she desires, considering the assets she has used (If she owns them or another person has the rights over derivative works), and generate the NFT to publish into the marketplace.
7. She puts a price to the content generated.

Once the content is sold the amount that she deserves is added to her wallet and the part that other creators deserve is addressed to their wallets.

4.1.7 Scenario 1.2 - Students from MMU School of Digital Arts

4.1.7.1 Summary

SODA creative media student working as part of team must produce artwork using NWFA and other footage from SODA Commons (DAO) for community arts event organised as part of DAFNE+ testing – gallery exhibition.

Note: this is a *scenario* in the classic UX sense of being a singular example that through its specific characteristics provides context that is applicable to similar scenarios, i.e. other students, other shows and other content providers.

4.1.7.2 Managed assets: Student artworks

Artworks can be hosted by the platform under DAFNE+ license or can be referenced by the platform with delegation of licenses to third party repositories or marketplaces.

File Types:

- Sound – MP3, Aiff, WAV
- Animation – GIFs, SVG
- Image – Jpg, Tiff, PNG
- 3D files – GLTF
- DotMax files
- Maya files (.MA)

4.1.7.3 Promotional materials

- Title
- Author
- Media Type / Multiple Media Type
- Thumbnail images of different quality versions (for music for example are there MP3 and WAV options or potentially different quality MP3s - 192 or 256 for previews).
- Year of work
- Image of the work
- Short musical excerpt (3-5 seconds)
- Short video excerpt (3-5 seconds)

4.1.7.4 User journeys

4.1.7.4.1 Content consumer

1. User logs into the platform and create or connect their wallet to interact with the assets of the platform.
2. Search into the platform for topics she likes.
3. Watches the content displayed on her screen and comments on the content.
4. When she really likes the content and want to reward the creator, buys a piece of content minting a NFT that is added to her wallet.

4.1.7.4.2 SODA creative media student

1. Student signs up to DAFNE+ platform using instructions given on the SODA website or in educational artistic brief they are set. They are not much invested at this point in SODA Commons and DAFNE+ platform and do not entirely understand what they will get out of it, (despite an explanation by their lecturer!)
2. They follow instructions to set up a crypto wallet and are able to associate it with their account. They are interested in the idea of a wallet for artworks and perhaps do a little more research into the idea at this point.
3. As part of their assignment, they must work on a project exploring the history of an area of Manchester, using the NWFA and other assets to tell a story. They search DAFNE+ refining their search to SODA Commons, NWFA and/or other terms to narrow search results.
4. They use the AI content filter to refine their search results for video interviews in color (or other content features that are relevant/possible in DAFNE+).
5. They find assets that they want to work with, then use the inbuilt credit system to download the work, storing the transaction within the blockchain, along with relevant rights management information (i.e., a pro forma contract agreement).
6. They use the content in a collaborative project with others in their transdisciplinary group and once it is complete, they are able to mint an NFT (or other tokenised blockchain representation) of their project. This might be:
 - a. a single asset, e.g., a film or 3D asset like an environment based on historical footage.
 - b. a configuration of assets, e.g., a film, a 3D asset, a projection mapping sequence and a performance script
 - c. Documentation of a project, e.g., a video of the installation being developed and its final outcome.

7. The student-centred event takes place. The students advertise their work as being available on the DAFNE+ platform and are excited to see that someone has bought an edition of their work during the event. Someone else online has downloaded it to view.
8. They post documentation of the exhibition on their Tiktok account and also decide to mint that to the SODA Commons.
9. After the event, they agree as a group to grant a three-year educational licence for others to view and use work. They are secure in the knowledge that it will not be used without their knowledge or in commercial contexts.

4.1.7.4.3 Secondary user journey: content provider, NWFA

1. The NWFA is contacted prior to the project to provide a package of relevant footage from the collection for a project on Manchester's history. It chooses footage for which it has most control over rights and can easily sign off as part of the tiered system of SODA Commons.
2. A member of the team signs up to DAFNE+ platform and mints individual pieces of content (ideally via batch process) as custodian on behalf of content owners.
3. The member of the team checks the metadata about each piece of media that has been generated by the content algorithm and is able to make text changes to one or two that incorrectly label certain aspects and delete erroneous labelling.
4. Once students start choosing footage from the package (via DAFNE+), the NWFA team member receives notifications and a records page allows them to track the individuals who are currently using the footage in their work. Derived works added to the SODA Commons (via DAFNE+) are also tracked.
5. If derived works are sold, DAFNE+ automatically processes the transaction providing the requisite fraction of the earnings to NWFA for distribution.

4.1.7.4.4 Secondary user journey: staff

1. Staff sign up with the DAFNE+ platform and use it to browse existing content and make lists of recommended assets for use in an upcoming project.
2. These are included as links in the assignment brief.
3. After discussing requirements with content partner, NWFA they are able to review content uploaded prior to sharing with students, probably by searchable tags.

4.1.7.4.5 Secondary user journey: audience

1. At event, audience member uses QR code to be taken to a project/asset page via DAFNE+.
2. Having viewed the terms and conditions and description of content, they decide to buy an edition and are directed to create a wallet if they do not already have one and purchase the asset through the marketplace transaction managed by DAFNE+.
3. An NFT edition is minted and added to their wallet.

4.2 Use-case 2 - Experimental sound/music production

4.2.1 Summary

The DAFNE+ Use-case 2 - Experimental sound/music production builds on and extends IRCAM's corporate framework of articulation of technological research and contemporary artistic production. The addressed community includes on one side researchers, engineers, and companies involved in the production of creative technology, and on the other side artists and creatives using this technology including composers, performers, sound designers, and computer music designers. The use-case also brings another category of users not part of IRCAM's community: NFT collectors and art sponsors. The focus is on live interactive computer music, but with more and more extensions to the use of advanced sound and music technologies in other creative areas including performing arts, installations, sound design, etc. Therefore, the use-case title was extended to explicitly including this sound creative dimension present in other activity sectors than music. A specificity of the use-case in the emerging landscape of blockchain/NFT based platforms for sound and music, related to the "experimental" attribute, is that the assets to be managed are not only fixed media such as sound files of music or sound recordings, but pieces of code and related data necessary for the (re)production of sound/music artworks, especially when they are interactive, and also more complex fixed media audio/music formats currently not supported in other blockchain platforms, such as for multichannel audio.

The use-case is structured in 3 scenarios based on the assets to be managed:

1. Creation and use of components
2. Creation and use of work repositories
3. Creation and use of works / private spaces

The scenarios are presented in more detail in the following sections.

4.2.2 Background to Use-case 2 scenarios

4.2.2.1 The IRCAM art-science-technology framework

The Institute for Acoustic/Music Research and Coordination IRCAM is today one of the largest public research centers in the world articulating musical creation and scientific research. A unique place where artistic foresight and scientific and technological innovation converge. IRCAM's original framework as an organization has been since its inception in 1977, as a component of the Centre Pompidou's project, to gather researchers, engineers and artists in a single place and organize productive interactions between them. Its research lab entitled STMS (Science and Technology of Music and Sound) gathers 100-150 researchers, faculty and engineers specialized in all scientific fields related to music and sound. The artistic and production departments commission and host some of the greatest composers of our time for producing 30 new artworks every year, mostly live performance music pieces based on IRCAM's latest technology. Beyond the presence of artists, a specificity of the lab in the academic world is indeed that most research teams include engineers who develop and maintain over years dozens of technical environments and modules (mostly software but also hardware) that integrate new research results and make them available to artists for their own production. In addition, IRCAM's technology is licensed to many companies, not only for music production tools but more broadly for audiovisual and multimedia production, music distribution, automotive, healthcare, etc.

4.2.2.2 The IRCAM technological ecosystem

For several decades, the main target environment for IRCAM's live performance production has been the [Max](#) (formerly Max/MSP) application, licensed to and marketed by the californian Cycling'74 company. Max

enables non-professional programmers to graphically program and execute real-time audio and music and image processing algorithms and their user control interfaces from a huge set of objects based on a published API. Most music pieces produced at IRCAM combining live performers and real-time computer processing are based on the development of a set of dedicated Max patches. Algorithms resulting from IRCAM's research are developed in C/C++ and made available to artists as new Max external objects, extending the existing features. In addition to Max as a runtime, Max patches can be developed as MaxForLive plugins to run in the Ableton Live environment, with a simpler user interface hiding the programming layers and making them available to a broad community of live electronic musicians.

Some of the objects developed for Max are also developed for the free, open-source sister environment **Pure Data**. The communities using Max and PureData are similar but do not always overlap.

Other computer languages are developed and used within Ircam for the development of programming environments. This is the case of LISP and LUA for the **Modalys** and **OpenMusic** environments (more than 100K downloads since its creation). The high-level asynchronous language **Antescofo** allows the control of **SuperCollider**, as well as other sound operators such as **FAUST**.

Finally, **Matlab**, **Python**, **C/C++** languages are widely used within the institute for the development of libraries and standalone software. A **git-based forge** is shared by the research teams to pool tools and resources for deep learning, continuous integration, and source code versioning.

4.2.2.3 The IRCAM Forum

The IRCAM Forum was founded 30 years ago in order to make the IRCAM non-commercial technology available to external users, mostly artists - composers, performers, sound designers, sound engineers, but also researchers and teachers, engineers, etc. The main vectors for this interaction between IRCAM research teams as technology producers and these users are the forum.ircam.fr web platform and the organisation of the IRCAM Forum Workshops gathering part of the community every year at IRCAM and in various countries in collaboration with partner institutions. From a platform of distribution of IRCAM technology, the Forum website turned from 2019 to a community platform, enabling members to publish their own content (software distributions, articles) and exchange in specialised discussion groups and collaborate through an internal gitlab. An important component of the IRCAM Forum is also to manage the documentation and promotion of the technology through the editorial production of related tutorials, teasers, user documentations in various forms (text documents, sound examples, videos, etc.). Technology distribution in the Forum platform is done through *Projects* that can include any set of digital elements including code and data, examples, tutorials, etc. in dedicated archives. Projects can be created directly in the platform CMS, as well as mirrors from external distribution repositories such as GitHub.

The IRCAM Forum current license is based on a yearly registration divided into 3 categories:

- **IRCAM Forum Free license:** Free access to most of the technology and to documentation and community features for personal and non-commercial use (except for artistic production).
- **IRCAM Forum Premium Individual license:** Premium membership costs 200€/year (100€ for students) and in addition to Free registration gives exclusive access to some of the cutting-edge software for music production and reduced fees to events, trainings, partner's products and other goodies.
- **IRCAM Forum Premium Institutional license:** Group license for academic institutions (conservatories, universities, music schools, research studios and centers, art-science programs), companies, music production studio etc. Premium membership costs 1000€/year and gives exclusive

access to some of the cutting-edge software for music production and reduced fees to events, partner's products and other goodies. In addition, the license allows for professional use within education programs and studio's equipment.

The principle of the license is that members have access to projects' updates and new projects during the yearly period of registration, and keep after it a license of use of already installed software.

4.2.2.4 Brahms/Sidney: Work repositories

The IRCAM Forum is focused on tools for artistic production. In addition, IRCAM manages through its Sidney internal platform a private database of all versions of work repositories produced at IRCAM containing archives of all the digital elements needed to perform interactive pieces (patches, sounds, documentations, etc.). More broadly in the international computer music community, and despite various expressed marks of interest and related studies there has been up to now no large scale published database of experimental sound/music work repositories.

4.2.3 Key findings from the user-feedback process

4.2.3.1 Blockchains and NFTs

Most users are not familiar with blockchains/NFT and can hardly figure out what they can get from them. However, in interviews and workshops, after a presentation of the DAFNE+ and the UC2's starting offer, they seemed open to these new proposals, often ended up to new ideas that have fed our use-case specification, and expressed the wish to reflect more in-depth about these possibilities.

4.2.3.2 Publication and access to/use of components/ new creation tools

The related features are for most of them already in place in IRCAM's Forum organization.

IRCAM Forum's component users already have access to dozens of advanced creative technologies, in addition to all the existing open source and commercial offers that are quite rich.

As for software developers/publishers, the various distribution options including open source (GitHub), IRCAM Forum license and commercial licenses satisfy most of the needs and the potential added value of a blockchain/NFT based platform for software distribution and monetization is not obvious. In addition, most involved developers and researchers are employees and can't expect a direct financial benefit from new monetization schemes. So the interest of using blockchain/NFTs for creative software distribution remains uncertain at the current stage.

For this scenario, the development of the DAFNE+ platform should build on IRCAM's Forum and focus on the development of new features that emerge as potentially interesting advances for users, such as the use of the blockchain as a reference for formalizing authorship (individual or collective) on creative software production as an alternative to software deposit.

4.2.3.3 Publication and access to/use of work repositories

The management of these assets represents the newest dimension of UC2's initial offer and a significant part of exchanges with users focused on it. There has been indeed an interest expressed by interviewed artists on the following aspects:

- Use of the blockchain for the formalisation of artwork authorship, in particular for artists applying to public calls.
- Setting and publishing an unparalleled database of work repositories and contributing to the cultural heritage of experimental/contemporary sound/music artistic production. This interest is strongly conditioned to sufficient guarantees to be given on the platform sustainability beyond the project's

timeframe. This objective is a priori not part of IRCAM's missions so this sustainability will be effective at the end of the project if a new, sustainable organization is ready to manage the related DAO.

- In the musicological field including not only researchers but also artists, there is a strong interest in getting access to the technical and algorithmic insights of remarkable artwork beyond the musical surface. Some are ready to pay for this access, even if the scope and market is potentially limited. Moreover, the availability of such a database opens new possibilities of tracking the influences of artistic ideas from one work to another. Although the expressed expectation of automatically tracking these relations seems unrealistic technically, it could be based on voluntary declarations of artist's influences from one work to another.
- The users emphasized the importance of the quality of the technical documentation necessary for enabling the work performance on the basis of the elements included in the repository. This situation relates to a typical case for works for single instrument+electronics where a performer plans to perform the work and misses necessary information. It appears that artists are mostly focused on their artistic production and promotion and few of them on the afterward process of sustainability of their works. A high standard of structured documentation of repositories is needed and expectations were expressed from IRCAM to elaborate a template on the basis of its documentation standards and validation workflows.
- There are legal obstacles for artists to publish their repositories in some cases, bound in particular by agreements between composers and score publishers: technical repositories of interactive music works including instrumental parts are considered to be part of publishers' exclusivity; publishers as traditional companies focused on sheet paper editing and printing are not necessarily open to new technologies. Alternatives exist, like digital score publishing cooperatives and companies. Moreover, many concerned artists don't have a score publisher and are free to publish their work repositories.
- As a consequence, different positions were expressed on the default publication of work repositories: some wish them to be publicly available by default and others condition their publication to approval processes that may imply a financial counterpart and/or an assessment of the capacity of the licensee to respect the initial artistic intention when performing the piece.
- Similar reserves and conditions may apply to the production of new versions of repositories: they may be required by the initial repository creators whereas others will accept any community proposals: these options shall be available to them in the DAO.
- A feedback from several repository owners (be them related to individual or collective artistic production) is that they may wish to manage locally their own assets storage, so that in case of a stop of the global platform they still keep their own assets.
- The monetization possibilities for this scenario seem quite limited if the involved community remains restricted to the one of experimental sound/music. Unlike visual arts, there are, at least in Europe, very few private sponsors for this artistic area. So a condition for enabling the adoption of new monetization schemes for this scenario is to extend the involved community, on one side by addressing other artistic fields such as interactive and/or sound art, and on the other side by connecting this artistic ecosystem to the one of NFTs and blockchains; this latter aspect is identified as a major challenge at DAFNE+ 's project level. In addition, what emerged from the exchanges as potential value was that it should be rather oriented to new artistic productions, with people buying NFTs for getting privileged access to the production of a new artwork. The potential added value is then not necessarily on the work repositories but on other assets, so this led us to elaborate a third

scenario based on these new assets, even if this scenario was not presented as such for the user feedback process.

4.2.3.4 Creation and obtention of private ownership/access to an artwork

Being associated with the creation of a new artwork can be an important motivating factor for NFT collectors. Related experiments already exist for mainstream recorded music in many marketplaces and specialised platforms such as French startup [Pianity](#). The first ideas that emerged from interviews included:

- The production of limited editions of an interactive music piece, each edition being possibly related to a unique variant of its parameters associated to a unique NFT.
- A privileged access as a sponsor to the piece production, possibly in several forms: VIP access to the performance premiere, privileged access to the artist (physical or remote meeting), publication of a mention in the communication supports related to the premiere announcement, etc.

Further exchanges with various concerned stakeholders enabled to complement these ideas and to come up to the definition of the 2.3 User scenario presented hereinafter, which was not foreseen in our initial specifications.

In particular exchanges with IRCAM's artistic and production directions evidenced the interest in DAFNE+'s platform offer rather for the creation of new artwork forms specifically designed for the new distribution medium it represents than for the inclusion of already existing works and for the constitution of a reference database of works repository, which is not part of IRCAM's corporate mission as a publicly funded institution.

4.2.4 Targeted users, assets, and usage

4.2.4.1 User roles

Users must have registered on the platform beforehand. Each member has a profile introducing him/her on the platform. User roles are defined in relation to the assets they manage. Technically, component, repository and work assets are similar. The three different scenarios result from three different uses of these assets. Also, for each scenario/asset type, there are author, collaborator, referencer and user roles. Each member of the platform is potentially a user and can have several roles, sometimes author, sometimes collaborator, sometimes referencer, depending on the assets managed.

The **Author** is the person responsible for the asset. The author is the administrator of the space linked to the asset and manages access, decides on the type of smart-contract, authorises and invites collaborators and access to its users. The author can decide at any time to delete his asset, according to the rules in force in the DAO/platform.

The **Collaborator** can be a co-manager or co-administrator of the asset, or a reviewer or co-developer, and cooperate on the different parts of the asset description. He can inherit part of the asset's value (distribution of NFTs among collaborators) at the transaction and can become the author if the latter wishes to pass on his leadership role. For some decisions, the collaborator and the author will have to agree (change of smart contract...). Consensus, majority vote or another decision strategy depending on the DAO will then be implemented.

The **Referencer** works as a community manager/facilitator, a moderator, a spam cleaner and a content organiser. This role can classically be assigned to one person within the platform's administration, to several people depending on the community, or even be distributed among several users according to the rules given by the platform's DAO.

In addition to the most classical tasks of a digital community manager, the referencer can integrate components, repositories or works from other platforms into the DAFNE+ platform. After agreeing with the authors of these contents, the referencer creates a "mirror asset" whose content (description, files...) directly inherits from third-party containers. For example, the library spat, present on the Forum is referenced by the DAFNE+ platform. The description, as well as the download of the installation files of the library remain located on the Forum website but are accessible on the DAFNE+ platform which uses links or APIs of third-party platforms (GitHub, gitlab, bitbucket...)

The **User** is the consumer of the platform. He/she owns a wallet and can "adhere" to components, repositories and works. By purchasing or subscribing to an asset, according to the rules of the DAO, the user implicitly signs a smart contract with the author and the collaborators of the asset. The user therefore buys access, use, ownership, reproduction and monetization rights specific to each asset.

4.2.4.2 Managed assets

Asset types: There are three main types of assets involved in the making and dissemination of code-based sound/music work. The work of creation rests on the use of functionalities of various **components** existing beforehand. These components are elements which have a generic character and whose use is not circumscribed to the reproduction of a work in particular. The creation phase produces tools that are specific to the creation of a work or a series of works. Some of these tools can be extracted and generalized in the form of new generic components. The creation process results in a set of technical elements, called a **repository**, composed of execution programs based on generic components and on data specific to the work. The documentation allows to arrange these elements in order to reproduce the work. The diffusion of this **work** can today be multimodal, multiple and fragmentary. In the space of digital diffusion, it can be reduced to a simple link, or be accompanied by related data and available to a restricted set of "spectators".

Assets can be composed of {scripts, codes, patches + media, sound, video + documentation, tech rider}. They design together a set of technical assets allowing the reproduction and or the generation of a work. The asset manager allowing the repository of components and directories must allow the storage of files of several types, program, binary, data. Some files can potentially be large: for example, a sound media file of several hours with several channels.

Relations between assets: An asset (component or repository) can be integrated or referenced by another asset and/or by a new version of the asset. Inheritance and dependencies between assets can be declared by authors, in a statement of good faith, allowing for retroactive crediting via the blockchain: it seems to be the best way to link the dependencies between assets with the reward, reputation and monetization system. Thus, in the declaration of ownership of an asset by an author, the latter can declare that such a percentage comes from another asset or even declare that such a percentage comes from a collaborator.

Versioning: The management of components/repositories must be possible individually and collectively and must allow versioning and forking. The versioning system contribute to the sustainability of the repositories, and thus of the platform itself as an answer to the rapid obsolescence of software environments.

Collaborative versioning seems to be a relevant option in certain cases; not yet adopted by users, the virtues seem nevertheless appreciated and valued. A formal (implementation independent) description of the functionalities can also improve the long-term durability.

Asset Documentation: When making components/repositories publicly available, users recognize the importance of documentation: "Yes, documentation is crucial and underrated" vs. "Have always wanted to but lack the time". Documentation seems to be necessary prior to publication. However, since it is optional and time-costly, it tends to be wasted. A moderation system based on peer-to-peer reviews would promote better

documented projects and thus encourage the quality of documentation indirectly/directly. **The peer review mechanism**, like the fight against spam, in short, the **moderation** of new content must be carefully thought out in a self-maintaining platform by these users.

4.2.5 DAO related rules

Few feedback was expressed till now from our community that may feed the DAO specification. What emerged concerns various positions expressed by asset owners on the way they would like to make them available, which should be foreseen as different options offered to them in the DAO rules:

- Ownership: Identification of the right owners and their respective shares in the asset.
- Asset publication conditions: published by default, or conditional to financial counterpart such as NFT acquisition and/or case-by-case validation by asset owners.
- Scalable user-license:
 - Own Usage: Defines the possible use of the asset by users.
 - Redistribution: Defines the rights and conditions of redistributing the asset.
 - Versioning, forking: allowing anyone to produce a new version/a new fork from the asset, or only upon a validation process by right owners. The motivation behind this latter case is to ensure the integrity of the initial artistic intention through the selection of trusted users.
- Monetization options:
 - Prices for primary and secondary markets.
 - Split of income between right owners including initial asset creators and creators of subsequent versions, DAO members, platform management...

4.2.6 Scenario 2.1 – Creation and use of components

4.2.6.1 Scenario description

Components authors (developers of creative functions and tools) store their assets on existing platforms like github, gitlab or IRCAM Forum for archiving, sustainability, publication, self-promotion or sale. They also see it as a practical way to make assets available for collective activities such as co-creation, workshop support or academic publication. In a spirit of sharing and building their professional reputation, more and more researchers and creators are publishing creative code, open-source libraries or free applications. Whether it's selflessly distributing tools to artists and creatives, or more directly assisting artists in their production work by releasing new features of an existing library, or publishing a courseware with code to be executed, component authors appreciate the advantages brought by collective management platforms for asset versioning. These platforms have recently integrated mechanisms for sponsorship between their members ([github](#) since June 2022 for instance). More and more independent developers are using sites like [Patreon](#) to distribute their releases only to people who have subscribed to a paid membership. Finally, some authors of creative libraries do not hesitate to create their own [e-commerce site](#) to sell applications and services.

Some are ready to try the NFTs adventure. But not everyone is ready to take the risk of a platform migration, especially if it is not proven and experimental like ours. So it seems necessary to think about an interaction mechanism between DAFNE+ and the existing platforms. For that, the IRCAM forum website integrates git functionalities and makes direct links to GitHub and other platforms (see [OpenMusic](#) for instance). These "mirror components" have the advantage of being created quickly by a **Component referencer**, without duplication of content and are always up to date. If a monetization mechanism is associated with this type of component, then the user will find an added value and will promote his/her library on the DAFNE+ platform. This will lead to a migration trend that could push these authors to use the platform, if the monetization aspect is more efficient than the sponsorship mechanisms of other platforms.

More generally, the approach for this scenario is to build on IRCAM's Forum, define ways of interfacing both frameworks by handling related technical and legal issues, and focus on the development of new features that emerge as potentially interesting advances for users:

- development of new advanced tools for sound/music processing and synthesis.
- Use of the blockchain as a reference for formalizing authorship (individual or collective) on creative software production as an alternative to software deposit.
- Enhanced management of component versioning and publication.
- Better support of collective work, be it on development including beta-testing, or in groupware for artistic production and/or education using components.
- Experimentation of new monetization schemes for creative software distribution.

4.2.6.2 User profiles

- Component Author: developer, researcher, company.
- Component Collaborator: collaborator in the development/maintenance of a component: creative in the loop, student, etc.
- Component Referencer: Person who creates a "mirror component", whose content and description are given by a third party site: DAFNE+/IRCAM Forum Admin, Community managers.
- Component User: creative – composer, computer music designer, sound engineer, performer...

4.2.6.3 Managed assets: Components

A component is a technical element whose integration gives access to generic functionalities. It is a high-level entity (package, library, compressed folder), grouping multiple files of heterogeneous data types: Standalone, application, software, libraries, program, script and patches: max library, max package, maxforlive device, puredata external, python, colab, AI model, 3D model, Sound bank, Dataset...

This element can be hosted by the platform under DAFNE+ license or can be referenced by the platform with delegation of license to a third party - Github, IRCAM Forum, bitbucket, third party websites. Example components provided as part of WP3 are:

- [Dicy2](#) library: Max Package for music generativity and improvisation .
- [CoMo](#) and [SoundWorks](#) libraries: javascript and apps for collective interaction with distributed audio/music devices.
- [Spat](#) library: Max Package for sound spatialisation.
- [RAVE, RAVE2 and nn~](#): Python script and Max Package for deep learning for sound synthesis/processing.

4.2.6.4 Promotional materials

- Description of the asset using modern WYSIWYG interface including
 - Asset description: Tree of files and folder architecture, ReadMe...
 - Asset version: date of publication, version number, release notes.
 - Uploaded illustrations, jpg, gif, video...
 - Links to additional contents: Documentation, tutorials, website...
- Use license(s), monetization conditions
- Dependencies
 - List of contributors: author, collaborators, referencer...
 - Dependency tree of DAFNE+ internal and external assets.
 - Featured in (kindship with other components and repositories).

- Related asset (most proximate assets according to AI search engine).
- DAFNE+ platform context
 - DAO/Community/tribe.
 - Categories.
 - Tags.
- Social network:
 - Notification, follow-up.
 - Link to catalogues, Discord & other social networks.

4.2.6.5 User journeys

- **Component Author journey:** The Component Author uploads a new component, declares publication options (public/reserved to DAO/conditional to NFT ownership, etc.), describes it and manages group access.
- **Component Collaborator journey:** A Component collaborator can ask for access to the component. Once the Component Producer accepts, the Component collaborator can access the back office of the component, download it and upload a new version of it. The Component Producer can define the amount of co-authorship for each of the collaborators.
- **Component Referencer journey:** Component Referencer can create a component by referencing an existing one, possibly hosted by another platform. She links the download button to an existing URL and the description to an already existing content.
- **Component User journey:** After explicitly accepting the necessary conditions, Component User can download a component and use it to create a repository, an artwork, or another component.

4.2.7 Scenario 2.2 – Creation and use of work repositories

4.2.7.1 Scenario description

Artists, creatives, archivists, musicologists, music/sound producers need a shared database of the technical elements that intervene in the production or reproduction of artworks. A frequent setup for mixed music works combining instruments on stage and computer generated sounds or processes concerns the programs, the related data and the technical configuration needed to execute the piece during the performance.

In addition, some artists no longer conceive works in the sense of fixed artefacts, but in the form of generative processes that allow the creation of a virtually infinite number of works. This is particularly true in the age of artificial intelligence-assisted creation. Also, these authors are interested, not in selling their works, but rather in selling access to the generative machine allowing the synthesis of new works, which they are certain can be signed in their name. Thus the platform should allow the management of access to these generative machines, creative application/process, synthesizer, transcoder... This last field of application seems relatively new and particularly in phase with the development of NFTs.

4.2.7.2 User profiles

- Repository Author: Mainly artists – composers, computer music designers, sound designers
- Repository Collaborator: Collaborator in the development/maintenance of a Repository. Same profiles.
- Repository Referencer: Person who creates a "mirror Repository", whose content and description are given by a third party site. Same profiles, plus DAFNE+/IRCAM Admin and Community managers.
- Repository User:
 - Composer, computer music designer, sound engineer, sound designer

- Music performers (individuals, ensembles, orchestras), performing artists, music and art venues, score publishers, sponsors.
- Musicologist and archivist

4.2.7.3 Managed assets: work repositories

A technical element whose implementation allows the production or reproduction of a specific work. A repository is a high-level entity (compressed folder, dmg, zip file), grouping multiple files of heterogeneous data types: A zip, a dmg file or a folder that contains the code, programs, data, library dependencies, documentation (including published score), and any other references or metadata to implement a creative process. The repositories usually contain, together with all needed programs and data, the following documentation:

- Differences with previous versions if any.
- Installation instructions.
- Tech rider and hard/software combination.
- System calibration and tests.
- Initialization routine.
- Technical instructions.
- Performance notes/score.
- Notes for the people who will open this documentation in 2050.

4.2.7.4 Promotional materials

- Description of the work using modern WYSIWYG interface including:
 - Work description: title, author(s), date of creation.
 - Basic work presentation, including link to work documentation such as in the IRCAM [Brahms](#) contemporary music works database.
 - Audio or video excerpt of work performance.
- Description of the asset including
 - Asset description: Tree of files and folder architecture, ReadMe...
 - Asset version: date of publication, version number, release notes.
 - Links to additional contents: documentation, tutorial, website...
- Use license(s), monetization conditions.
- Dependencies.
 - List of contributors and right owners: author, collaborators, referencer, score publisher.
 - Dependency tree of DAFNE+ internal and external assets.
 - Featured in (kindship with other components and repositories).
 - Related asset (most proximate assets according to AI search engine).
- DAFNE+ platform context
 - DAO/Community/tribe
 - Categories
 - Tags
- Social network:
 - Notification, follow-up,
 - Link to catalogues, Discord & other social networks

4.2.7.5 User journeys

4.2.7.5.1 Publication of a Repository

The Repository Author:

1. creates a repository in the CMS (git push / pull)
2. uploads a local package into the CMS (option to create a git repository, eventually goes to IPFS without repository)
3. defines publication options:
 - public/reserved to DAO/conditional to NFT ownership
 - NFT value
 - forking options
 - user-license
4. defines version of the repository as a release linked to a particular commit of the repository
5. defines ownership of the Repository version
 - Split of Repository version IP between various contributors (as registered users).
 - Possibility of allowing a percentage of ownership (credit) to existing components/repositories.
 - After the sale of the corresponding NFT, the contributors gets the same money as a percentage of the total value.
6. describes the repository with promotional material in the CMS with audio/video player, web interface to work performance, etc.
7. describes the repository with used components and every dependency of the application of the repository code
8. [Possible step] Assessment of the quality of the repository by peer-review / moderation by a moderator
9. uploads new versions in the CMS with content versioning management.

After the publication, the platform automatically announces the creation of a new repository for advertisement - featured in catalogues, Discord & social networks.

4.2.7.5.2 Publication of a new version of the Repository / Maintenance of a Repository:

Repository collaborator requests access to the Repository Producer according to DAO rules and publication options. The Repository Producer (owner) accepts or denies the request (the decision implies all stakeholders if numerous).

Repository Referencer journey: the Repository Referencer can create a Repository by referencing an existing one, possibly hosted by another platform. She links the download button to an existing URL and the description to an already existing content.

4.2.7.5.3 Use of a Repository

The Repository User:

1. buys an NFT
2. obtains the rights to use the repository according to publication options and DAO's rules.
3. downloads a zip file
4. can fork the repository as a new repository (GitHub, GitLab, etc.) if allowed.

4.2.8 Scenario 2.3 – Creation and use of works / private spaces

4.2.8.1 Scenario description

This third scenario emerged from exchanges with community experts as a potentially relevant approach for promoting and monetizing artistic creation with NFTs through various forms of direct exchanges between artists and their fans and/or sponsors and collectors in the cultural sector. Some of the artists give access to beta versions of their works using Patreon. Others had the opportunity during the time of the Covid-19 pandemic to perform private concerts in virtual rooms with limited access time and number. Others, including artists and their producers, are looking for new ways of sponsoring beyond work commissions to ensure complementary income and develop relations with fans interested in crowdfunding. More globally, NFT-based artwork distribution opens a new space of cultural exchanges that will foster new forms of works in the field of contemporary creation. In this scenario, work authors/producers are proposed to manage private digital spaces in which exclusive resources ranging from goodies to autographed works will be offered in exchange for sponsorship based on NFTs.

4.2.8.2 User profiles

A work author or producer creates a private space and invites people to join it according to the conditions defined in the DAO. A user of the private space who has bought an NFT can enter the private space and access exclusive content.

4.2.8.2.1 Creator/manager of a private space

An artist or creative and or his/her producer who wants to exchange exclusive content with her/his fan base/sponsors.

4.2.8.2.2 Work user: Buyer of a Work / Subscriber to a private space

- General public
- Art sponsor, NFT collector
- Cultural institution, performance venue

4.2.8.3 Managed assets

Here the qualification as an asset is questionable. In this use-case, the attribution of an NFT can concern either on a persistent resource in the blockchain such as a work or an ephemeral advantage such as an event ticket related to the work. Moreover, an important objective being to propose new ways of sponsoring a work in progress during its conception and production process, like crowdfunding, the scenario should enable to define a counterpart related to a notion of work project, not only to an already completed work.

In all cases, the counterpart to the NFT will be defined by the private space owner and directly managed by him/her with his/her subscribers.

For instance, for various forms of subscription to a work such as:

- Exclusive ownership of the work (unique sponsor).
- Shared ownership of the work, ownership of a limited edition of the work (multiple sponsors).
- Exclusive ownership of a unique variant of the work (parametrized work).

counterparts may include:

- VIP access to work performance premiere.
- Access to the artist (private session).
- Personal dedication published with the work premiere documentation.

- Public sponsoring exposure.
- Use license (possibly time limited) of work repository for work performance.
- Tickets for performance/concert.
- Access to the artworks “internals”, i.e. underlying production algorithms.
- Behind the scene, exclusive stories and content.

4.2.8.4 Promotional materials

- Description of the work using modern WYSIWYG interface including:
 - Work description: title, author(s), date of creation.
 - Basic work presentation, including link to work documentation such as in the IRCAM [Brahms](#) contemporary music works database.
 - Audio or video excerpt of work performance if already existing.
- Description of the private space (free text entered by owner).
- Monetization conditions.
- DAFNE+ platform context
 - Community/tribe
 - Categories
 - Tags
- Social network:
 - Notification, follow-up,
 - Link to catalogues, Discord & other social networks

4.2.8.5 User journeys

4.2.8.5.1 Creation of a Work private space

A Private space Creator:

- Creates a private space.
- References a work.
- Specifies the private space content.
- Defines NFT price following the DAO rules.
- Invites Work collaborators and Work Users to share/visit the private space.

4.2.8.5.2 Use of a Work/Work project private space

A Work user:

- can buy a NFT to access a private space.
- Respect conditions of the DAO.

4.3 Use-case 3 - Novel forms of artistic content exploitation

4.3.1 Summary

Use Case number three, led by the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC), is looking to explore possible alternative economic models based on emerging technologies for design practitioners and maker communities. IAAC facilitates the connection to Fab Lab Network, Distributed Design, etc. and other closely interconnected communities like creative individuals, educators, academics, art collectors, art curators, researchers, and managers.

IAAC is an open, independent non-profit educational research institution founded in 2003, based in Barcelona (Catalonia, Spain). IAAC is also an innovation hub that includes the research centre for digital fabrication Fab Lab Barcelona, which was the first Fab Lab funded in Europe in 2007, and still, today is one of the leading laboratories in the network of Fab Labs (affiliated with MIT's Center for Bit and Atoms) offering various programs and research initiatives that explore the intersection of innovative design, computation, and fabrication technologies fostering a culture of open collaboration and knowledge sharing to enable individuals to transform their ideas into tangible prototypes using digital fabrication technologies such as 3D printing, laser cutting, and CNC milling. The Distributed Design Platform acts as an exchange and networking hub for the emerging field of distributed design that promotes a decentralized and collaborative approach. It emphasizes the use of open-source design methodologies and digital fabrication technologies to enable local production and reduce the environmental impact of global supply chains promoting a decentralized and sustainable approach to design and production.

4.3.2 Background to Use-case 3 scenarios

The community within the Distributed Design network consists of designers, makers, craftspeople, and artists who utilize technology to create innovative forms of production that are locally productive and globally connected. Their approach is rooted in the core values of the Distributed Design Platform, which include being open, collaborative, regenerative, and ecosystemic in their practices.

These practitioners are actively involved in the emerging field of Distributed Design. Distributed Design is a novel approach to design which utilises global connectivity to move data instead of products and challenges traditional notions of how goods are produced and the materials used, with the goal of enhancing the customer's relationship with their products.

The participants in Use Case 3 scenarios encompass a diverse group of advanced users, including makers, designers, artists, researchers, material developers, and students. The community also includes other entities such as Fab Labs, cultural organizations, universities, and makerspaces.

Based on the surveys and interviews conducted for the project, it has been discovered that the community is composed of individuals with diverse profiles, yet they all share the same values and methodology. These profiles range from individual practitioners, self-employed entrepreneurs, freelancers, and researchers to students.

Use Case number three recognizes that there is no distinction between established or semi-professional businesses (both employees and freelancers) and those who pursue Distributed Design as a side job to supplement their income. What unites all these profiles is their shared passion for experimenting with innovation, emerging technologies, and the innovative application of creative and distributed tools. This includes the integration of blockchain technology into their practices.

4.3.3 Key findings from the user feedback process

The profiles of Use Case 3 are mainly within the Maker community connected to the Fab Lab Network, Distributed Design Member network and the extended connected community, which includes, for example, designers, academics, teachers/educators, art lovers, art collectors, art curators, researchers, managers.

The people Use Case 3 interact with are mostly aligned with the values of Open Source "movement" in the field of Design. However, at this stage is relevant to the purpose that the types of users and their roles resulting from the surveys and interviews are mainly multidisciplinary profiles; this would reflect and affect their potential interaction with the platform as:

- Repository/Component creator (Creator of a repository which is locally stored or hosted on a third-party library Github, Gitlab etc.) > value verification/revenue.
- Repository/Component User (User who mints component for further usage or adaptation) > version control.
- Repository/Component Contributor (User who has minted component and contributes with bug fix or adaptation to the original or new repository) > version control/revenue.

It is valuable for the future development of the platform to underline the position of most of the people in the network: self-employed entrepreneurs, freelancers, people who rely on research project grants, and students. Concluding that Use Case 3 community comprehend established/semi-professional businesses (both employee and freelancing), people who work with art/design/craft as a side to external income (needed for "make a living"), and creatives experimenting with innovation and emerging technologies. In this regard, it has been suggested to avoid creating a distinction between professionals and non-professionals as two separate categories, as it would raise questions such as: How would they eventually be defined? What criteria would be used to determine their capability to sell or generate income or should their motivation and passion be considered as social value?

This offers diversified potentials: projects and designs 100% Open Source or partially (when connected with capacity training programmes). Other projects/designs are offered to be bought prebuilt/made while also being provided Open Sourced to be replicated and improved.

To add to this, in discussions among members of the creative community, it has been mentioned that it would be interesting to make the platform appealing to individuals who possess technical expertise and knowledge related to blockchain, NFTs, and DAOs, even if they may lack the creative or artistic input themselves. Therefore, they would be happy to support the artists with their capabilities. Another interaction mentioned and follows this last example is for other users outside the "creative" bubble but who is the target of creatives products. Is there a way that also for them DAFNE+ is an appealing platform to interact with (maybe to connect directly with creators)?

There have been prevalent requests to integrate the platform with other commonly used tools in the workflow, such as Github, Gitlab, Wikifactory, or other open-source platforms. However, it has been noted that these platforms are not completely open-source and tend to dominate the space for those interested in open-source concepts. This monopoly eventually led to the exploitation of the free content for commercial purposes by the same platform itself (example of AI code generated by the free-community-based content available in Github). Transparency on the use and legal frame of the content is crucial. e.g. "it's important to distribute the power of free knowledge".

Generally, the offer of human body/parts and artistic style did not find any relevant comments. Instead has been mentioned that it is not related to any of our interviewees. Eventually, environmental images, textile mesh, and objects for motion sequences could be more interesting to explore and play with.

The main social medias used are Instagram and LinkedIn. To publish their work, Use Case 3 community favour their personal website hosted by user-friendly platforms such as Squarespace, WordPress, Shopify, Etsy, BigCartel etc. Again is meaningful the blurred boundaries between private and professional life. (see also above some concerns in relation to publishing).

The people Use Case 3 interacted with do not fully understand the key concepts (blockchain, NFTs, DAO) connected to DAFNE+. However, they mention that they would be curious to know more about it and start using it at the condition by which the platform is easily accessible in terms of a technical and financial low entry-level barrier.

They all agree that easy user engagement in terms of interface and experience is fundamental, followed by visible and explicit social and environmental values different from existing ones (it's been pointed out that the use of catchy words such as "fair", "sustainable", "open-source" should be better explained and framed within the motivation behind the platform).

It is important to highlight that even if DAFNE+ is an EU project, the users would need extra guarantees in terms of trust while using the platform for selling/distributing/exchanging money and for the platform's sustainability after the project's conclusion.

Although the people interviewed feel part of a strong community and are actively engaged online and offline with their peers, they have yet to learn how this can be translated as DAOs' engagement and management. Only one person, out of curiosity, was interested in investing time to explore the potentiality of a platform that would eventually have a short life. Another person mentioned that true distribution and decentralization cannot be true if it goes through the "artificial scarcity" of the NFTs market system, e.g. "old rules applied to a new world - we need new models".

The community is most interested in business model solutions that would support them in adding value to Open Source licenses to gain extra income while supporting the community and protecting it from theft (easy language concerning legal issues). All the financial aspects need to be fair and transparent. (see above)

Many of the users work as part of a local and/or global team. Therefore tools that can facilitate the workflow in terms of organization, co-creation and sharing of project/knowledge are some of the most relevant characteristics that they see as an incentive to choose one platform over another (extra values when it is possible to define roles and permissions in terms of contributor/reviewer/viewer and is possible to easily search through tags and visualize and provide feedback to what is being uploaded).

The few people who had knowledge of NFTs and Blockchain find an important incentive to integrate the platform with 3rd-party software to import artefact created on DAFNE+ or vice versa directly.

The interoperability is fundamental to the compatibility with the already existing and trusted NFT marketplace and the ability of the platform to redistribute the transactions automatically (as revenues but also as a system of micro-donation for using free tools).

As a last note, one specific request that could answer as a potentially unique incentive to the maker community could be the choice of a creative tool dedicated to digital fabrication; this could be translated as the original file as NFTs to create a unique physical item, this possibility is still open to research and comments on what this can mean and how it can be implemented.

Another key aspect that would be an important incentive for Use case 3 is the simplicity of the documentation process, as it is one phase our community sees as one of the most critical parts of their practice. If a cross-platform tool could help prepare properly documented steps of the process, people would be interested in using it (see also above if these two could be eventually linked).

4.3.4 Targeted users, assets, and usage

All users in the Use Case Study 3 represent people from (1) Maker movement community connected to the Fab Lab Network) (2) Distributed Design Member network and (3) extended connected community. For example, designers, academics, teachers/educators, art lovers, art collectors, art curators, researchers, and managers. Although there are different communities represented in use case 3. There are some commonalities in how these users create, contribute, re-design, re-mix and share their designs, as they most commonly share the same Open Source mentality.

4.3.5 DAO related rules

- Technically and easily accessible
- Low financial entry-level barrier
- Easy user engagement: interface, experience
- Transparency: Explicit social and environmental values (with an understanding of what fair and sustainable means)
- Trust
- Sustainability after the project's conclusion

4.3.6 Scenario 3.1 - Repository/Component creator

4.3.6.1 Scenario description

A creative person has prototyped and designed through an iterative process a project and has decided to put their project into an Open Source repository. The design incorporates a “How to” guide. This guide includes instructions on how to realize the design (e.g. text file) and folders which are dedicated to different components of the overall design. Folders host e.g. 3D printing files for an enclosure, code for electronic components and files for cnc-mill hardware. The repository, including the “how to” guide and folders, are hosted on Github (third-party library) and the person would like also to host it on the DAFNE+ platform. For them, the easiest is to directly integrate their existing repository into the DAFNE+ platform. The different platforms would communicate so the user can simply update the data on e.g. GitHub, and it would also be updated on DAFNE+ (best case scenario). Using DAFNE+ is an added value for the user as they are open for additional verification of their work, they receive extra value as being the “original owner” and a transparent chain of adaptation and updates from other users are being logged and are visible on the platform (version control). Seeing re-mixed and new versions of their design, with local adaptations from other users, is of interest to the repository creator, as they see value in the enhancement of the original design idea.

4.3.6.2 User profiles

In accordance with the information outlined in subsection 4.3.4 on “Targeted users, assets, and usage”, it is important to emphasize that the targeted users, such as makers, designers, hackers, and crafters, are all part of a unified community represented by Use Case Study 3, which includes users from three main groups: the Maker movement community connected to the Fab Lab Network, the Distributed Design Member network, and the extended connected community. These individuals have various roles, including designers, academics, teachers/educators, researchers, and managers. Despite their diverse backgrounds, they share a common approach in the creation, contribution, redesign, remixing, and sharing of designs embracing an Open Source mentality.

4.3.6.3 Managed assets and promotional materials

- Repository: Folder/ Library containing a set of components and instructions
 - .md, json, .pdf, .txt, ... (Documentation includes free text, links, external sources, ...)
- Component A: File containing data to make component.
 - CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, DXF, SVG, Gcode, XTML...
- Component B: File containing code for e.g. electronic components

4.3.6.4 Promotional materials

The repository creator possibly is using external platforms to showcase their designs. For example social media platforms such as Instagram, or big cartel to sell part's of their design (components) or the whole design. The DAFNE+ profiles of users and repositories should offer space to link to those external websites. They might want to add images, or videos showing their work on their profile or in their repositories.

4.3.6.5 Legal, governance and monetization options

There is a need to address the challenges faced by repositories and content creators in the open-source community. While open-source licenses promote collaboration and sharing, it is essential to find ways to enable these creators to sustain their livelihoods and benefit from their contributions.

This means:

- Developing mechanisms that enable content creators to monetize their work while still promoting the principles of sharing and collaboration.
- Grant content creators the freedom to choose suitable copyright agreements for their work. This would empower them to decide how their creations can be used, whether it's for non-profit purposes or commercial applications.
- Guarantee fair and transparent pricing and payment systems through clear guidelines and mechanisms for valuing content creators' contributions and equitable distribution of earnings and proper recognition for the creators' work.
- Copyright infringement poses a significant threat to content creators, potentially resulting in substantial financial losses.

4.3.6.6 User journeys

1. User enters the platform and learns about DAFNE+
2. The user creates a profile because the added value through DAFNE+ is clear. They would like to engage with alternative business models for added value and additional sources of "income. They are interested in blockchain technology and how this could make a transparent chain of tracking changes and adaptations in designs.
3. User decides to upload a repository they have created potentially on a third-party library.
4. User will add a description of their project, possibly add images or videos from their project, and add links to external websites and platforms.
5. The user will assume that there will be some kind of explanation or visualisation of how their work will correlate with NFTs and Blockchain along the way.
6. The user may browse through other content creator profiles to explore other projects. For this, it would be useful to have a browse page in which users can choose e.g. tags to find projects/ repositories related to #music, #digitalfabrication #cncmilling or similar.
7. The user may also be interested in seeing geographically where other projects are to be able to collaborate locally on projects.

8. The user may want to write directly to other users.
9. The user may be interested in adding “interest” tags to their profile, so other users can identify their area of interest and expertise.

4.3.7 Scenario 3.2 – Repository/Component user

4.3.7.1 Scenario description

The user may be considered as “semi-professional” or a “hobbyist” and is interested in minting a component or a whole repository to re-create the whole project in their local setting. The user is mainly interested in browsing through the DAFNE+ website to explore other people's creations. They are eager to use tags or geolocation to find specific projects based on their interests, e.g. through tags. The user believes in Open Source principles and has a basic understanding of their implementations. The user will find it either through organic or direct search their desired project and will mint it/ download it and use its instructions to replication.

4.3.7.2 User profiles

In accordance with the information outlined in subsection 4.3.4 on “Targeted users, assets, and usage”, it is important to emphasize that the targeted users, such as makers, designers, hackers, and crafters, are all part of a unified community represented by Use Case Study 3, which includes users from three main groups: the Maker movement community connected to the Fab Lab Network, the Distributed Design Member network, and the extended connected community. These individuals have various roles, including designers, academics, teachers/educators, researchers, and managers. Despite their diverse backgrounds, they share a common approach in the creation, contribution, redesign, remixing, and sharing of designs embracing an Open Source mentality.

4.3.7.3 Managed assets

- Repository: Folder/ Library containing a set of components and instructions
 - .md, json, .pdf, .txt, ... (Documentation includes free text, links, external sources, ...)
- Component A: File containing data to make component.
 - CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, DXF, SVG, Gcode, XTML...
- Component B: File containing code for e.g. electronic components

4.3.7.4 Promotional materials

The user may not own their own repository on the DAFNE+ platform. The user may be interested in linking to their social media or other external pages/website already used in the workflow, such as Github, Gitlab, Wikifactory or other open-source platforms.

4.3.7.5 User journeys

1. The user enters the DAFNE+ platform
2. The users browse through the platform to understand the vision and the added values that DAFNE+ offers
3. The user enters a section of the platform that showcases the different creative works of DAFNE+ users. The content is shown potentially randomly or by “latest to be added” and the user scrolls through them to explore what the DAFNE+ community is working on.
4. The user is interested in finding a project to recreate.
5. The user uses the search function to find projects that work with #digitalfabrication, which are #easy to replicate and use #circularmaterials.

6. A page with different repositories from different users around the world is being shown, using the tags and an identification system.
7. The user can further define their search by tags that define the quality of the work done. e.g. some of the repositories created have earned badges from the DAFNE+ community for specifically well-made repositories, or for being great contributors.
8. The user visits some of the repository creator profiles to learn more about them and their work.
9. Based on the quality of the repository and the types of badges the repository creator has earned the user is choosing a repository to recreate.
10. The user is minting/downloading the repository and making it locally in their home/maker space or Fab Lab.

4.3.8 Scenario 3.3 - Repository/Component contributor

4.3.8.1 Scenario description

The user is a maker or designer who has experience in making projects and contributing to other projects. The user is a repository or component contributor, but they may also create repositories and components themselves. The user is interested in using the DAFNE+ platform because they know that added value through that. The platform offers transparent version control e.g. through blockchain technology, it offers a secondary revenue model through as they receive reputation and a type of monetary exchange for their contributions (to be discussed how this relates to NFT's).

4.3.8.2 User profiles

In accordance with the information outlined in subsection 4.3.4 on “Targeted users, assets, and usage”, it is important to emphasize that the targeted users, such as makers, designers, hackers, and crafters, are all part of a unified community represented by Use Case Study 3, which includes users from three main groups: the Maker movement community connected to the Fab Lab Network, the Distributed Design Member network, and the extended connected community. These individuals have various roles, including designers, academics, teachers/educators, researchers, and managers. Despite their diverse backgrounds, they share a common approach in the creation, contribution, redesign, remixing, and sharing of designs embracing an Open Source mentality.

4.3.8.3 Managed assets

- Repository: Folder/ Library containing a set of components and instructions
 - .md, json, .pdf, .txt, ... (Documentation includes free text, links, external sources, ...)
- Component A: File containing data to make component
 - CAD, OBJ, STL, STEP, DXF, SVG, Gcode, XTML...
- Component B: File containing code for e.g. electronic components

4.3.8.4 Promotional materials

The repository creator possibly is using external platforms to showcase their designs. For example social media platforms such as Instagram, or big cartel to sell parts of their design (components) or the whole design. The DAFNE+ profiles of users and repositories should offer space to link to those external websites. They might want to add images, or videos showing their work on their profile or in their repositories.

4.3.8.5 Legal, governance and monetization options

In the emerging field of open-source repositories and content contributors, it is important to focus on fair monetization and legal frameworks. To achieve these goals, it is necessary to:

- Explore alternative economic models that add value to open-source licenses and enable contributors to earn money from their work.
- Empowering contributors by adapting copyright agreements (have control over how their creations are used, whether for non-profit or commercial purposes).
- Establish a fair and transparent pricing and payment system.
- Be aware of how copyright infringement can damage repositories and content contributors' potential income.

4.3.8.6 User journeys

1. The user is entering the DAFNE+ platform, being a regular user.
2. The user is seeing the latest added repositories.
3. They potentially browse through those repositories to see if there is an interesting project to contribute to.
4. The user is reviewing their notifications to see if their proposed updates and changes have been reviewed and accepted by other users and repository creators.
5. The user has received a badge for being a contributor which is adding "valuable feedback" from x amount of other users. (The idea is that they receive a badge e.g. bronze, silver and gold after multiple users have verified the quality of their work).
6. The user has worked offline on some updates to another repository. They are now visiting the repository owner page to add their new contribution to the repository.
7. The user is commenting on the repository, adding additional files and images from the alteration and update.

5 Governance and monetization framework

The purpose of this chapter is to present a synthesis of the preliminary outcomes at the end of the first year of DAFNE+, of the research, carried out in the project in particular in the framework of WP6 on governance and monetization aspects in the perspective of the use-case specification.

5.1 Governance framework

DAFNE+ will offer means for democratic participation in the platform. This participation will be enabled by online tools that support general conversations and discussions about the platform and its community as well as specific tools to propose and vote for proposals that use the community funds of the DAO (See Monetization framework section). Following the most common DAO governance practices, DAFNE+ will offer web tools for conversations and discussion of the proposals (off-chain tools that don't interact with the blockchain), as well as blockchain enabled governance tools that allow users to make economic decisions of the DAO.

5.1.1 Chat

Online communities benefit from having channels for synchronous communication, meaning channels where members could expect a quick response and interaction for their messages. Indeed, many blockchain communities use chats as tools for community engagement, general and specific discussions, proposals, internal communication and coordination and more.

Discord is the most widely adopted chat platform for DAOs communities, and provide specific functionalities such as extensions and integrations with blockchain voting and reward systems.

5.1.2 Forum

Similar to other online communities, DAOs benefit from having dedicated spaces to make proposals and discuss them. The earliest and most technical communities, proposed and discussed these proposals using mailing lists and a git repository. For instance, Bitcoin established the Bitcoin Improvement Proposals to formalize the way to propose, improve, discuss and finally approve such proposals.

Many DAO communities use online forums for such discussions, the open source forum software Discourse being the most widely adopted. In these forums, proposals are discussed and improved, often in a phase that precedes the "on-chain" voting that will result in the proposal being officially accepted and executed by the DAO or rejected.

5.1.3 Proposals and voting

DAFNE+ platform will enable the community to make and vote proposals to make economic, development and community decisions. For making and discussing these proposals, the community will use forums, as previously discussed.

In order to solve the problem of low participation in DAOs governance, many projects have adopted platforms that enable secure voting on these proposals (only members of the DAO can vote) but that are free to use, unlike directly voting using a blockchain transaction that will cost each user a fee. The most widely used tool to handle proposals and voting for DAOs is snapshot (<https://snapshot.org/>).

In snapshot, communities can select between many available governance strategies. DAFNE+ platform will select one of these strategies and adapt it (if necessary) to the project needs.

The final tool selected for this functionality is still open for consideration.

5.2 Monetization framework

DAFNE+ platform will offer several economic functionalities for the creators and communities. One of the objectives of the project is to innovate on blockchain based economic models for the Cultural and Creative Industries. DAFNE+ will research the opportunities of this technology in three key functionalities: marketplace, redistribution mechanisms and collective fund management.

5.2.1 NFT Marketplace

One of the key functionalities of the platform for all the use cases is the NFT marketplace. In this marketplace, the content creators will be able to sell a wide diversity of content and software. Additionally, creators will be able to choose and sell different licenses for their content.

5.2.2 Redistribution and Fees

Most NFT platforms and marketplaces charge a transaction fee for their NFT sales. These fees vary from less than 1% to 15%. This disparity of accepted fees, together with the finding that our communities want to explore “taxation” and “redistribution” as means to create a fairer economy for the Cultural and Creative Industries, encourage the exploration and experimentation of redistributive economic models.

Thus, DAFNE+ will implement different fees that depend on the nature of the transaction and the wealth or value the transactions represent. Larger transactions and actors will be expected to contribute bigger fees to maintain the infrastructure and support the community initiatives that the community support using the DAO governance, as explained in next section.

Additionally, DAFNE+ will explore the feasibility of these fees as the main revenue stream for the platform economic sustainability.

5.2.3 DAO Funds: Grants, Prices, Community Initiatives, Proposals

DAFNE+ platform will implement a DAO. This DAO will be responsible for the governance of the platform, where users will decide on economic and governance models they want to adopt for their communities.

Our research on NFT Marketplaces shows us that the only active DAOs in the space are those that collectively manage funds. Thus, communities use DAOs if they perceive that their votes can be translated into actual economic support for their projects and proposals.

Thus, one of the key features of DAFNE+ platform will be the possibility to propose and fund proposals using the DAO funds and governance models. This feature will support the following uses:

- Internal funding: users will be able to propose and fund projects to improve DAFNE+
- External funding: users will be able to propose economic support to external projects, in the form of prize contests, grants for projects or community initiatives.

5.3 Initial economic and governance models

The innovation regarding the governance and economic models in DAFNE+ platform is one of the objectives of the project. Thus, the project will explore and propose alternatives, and test them with the pilot use cases. In the first phase of the project, however, DAFNE+ will adopt a basic economic and governance model to enable transactions and participation in the system. This proposal is based on the research on fair economic models (as part of T6.3) and the study of the ecosystem of NFT marketplaces, described with more in more details in D7.2.

These economic and governance models will be initially tested using testnets, to reduce the risks associated with using production blockchains with valuable cryptocurrencies in early stages.

5.3.1 Self-declaration of contributions for revenue sharing

Creators should be able to declare how revenues from NFT sales will be shared. The platform will enable to define the percentages that different creators will get from each sale.

Alternative models to explore in the future include using automatic recognition of contributions to calculate rewards for each artist (alike [SourceCred](#)), including social recognition systems of rewards like [praise](#), that allow the community to thank and reward any contributor, or using DAOs to calculate revenue sharing and participation ([sudoswap](#), [Commons Stack](#), [SPECTRE](#)).

5.3.2 Progressive platform fees

Platform fees have disappeared or drastically dropped after Blur Marketplace appearance. This has benefited investors and traders but it is unclear how this may benefit creators, that have seen their promised royalties for secondary sales disappear.

DAFNE+ platform will implement a progressive platform fee that depends on the amount of the transaction, ranging from a 0.1% to a 10% for larger sales.

5.3.3 Democratic platform governance

DAFNE+ DAO will enable democratic participation in the decisions of the platform. Each member will be able to make proposals and to have a vote. To qualify as a member, the user should be an artist selling at least one NFT in the platform. We will explore and consider other membership models, such as giving voting rights to collectors that acquired NFTs from different artists in DAFNE platform.

5.3.4 Collective fund management

DAFNE+ DAO will manage a collective economic fund. This fund will be governed with the DAO rules, that initially will give a vote for each token in the platform. Every member will be able to make proposals.

6 Use-case implementation strategy

6.1 Promotion

6.1.1 Value proposals and punchlines

The use-case leaders worked on sentences summarizing the platform value proposal and punchlines as engagement incentives for each scenario as a support of the promotional strategy, that are presented hereinafter.

6.1.1.1 Scenario 1.1- Prosumers in the Cultural Heritage

Value proposal : “Decentralized platform for fair creative **content distribution**. DAFNE+ empowers creators and communities through new digital distribution models based on digital tokens (NFTs).”

Based on "provenance" given by blockchain technologies, fair distribution of royalties, start earning since the minting (not need an audience like YT, or number of views.)

6.1.1.2 Scenario 1.2 - Students from MMU School of Digital Arts

Value proposal : “Be part of a passionate creative community offering an ethical approach to sharing assets and artworks”

Punchlines:

- **Protect your work online:** declaration of asset and artwork ownership through the blockchain.
- **Sell finished work as an NFT:** ability to monetize your work through NFT-based distribution.
- **Easier to collaborate:** work with other students from SODA, Manchester School of Art and Manchester Fashion Institute.
- **International reach:** connect with international artistic communities on the DAFNE+ network.
- **Better project documentation:** easy-to-use versioning of your project work.
- **Manage group projects:** group and collective work management.
- **Student-led, staff-supported:** Part of a student-led community, supported by your university staff.

6.1.1.3 Scenario 2.1- Creation and use of components

Value proposition: “Get access to /contribute to/ support latest audio/music technology for creative applications”; “A fair platform for sharing creative tools and works produced with them”.

Punchlines for component authors:

- **Blockchain based authorship:** Version your devs publicly while preserving authorship.
- **Monetize your devs:** get paid automatically when your devs are used by others.
- **User in the loop:** Enter into a synergistic relationship with your users.
- **Community building,** knowledge sharing, social interaction, groupware, advertisement, promotion, reputation

Punchlines for component users:

- **Get access** to latest audio/music technology for creative applications.
- **Blur the line between coding and creation** by integrating the latest creative technologies into your art production.
- **Artist in the loop:** Enter into a synergistic relationship with the developers.
- **Sponsor the authors** indirectly by purchasing components from them.

- **Community building**, knowledge sharing, social interaction, groupware, advertisement, promotion.

6.1.1.4 Scenario 2.2 - Creation and use of work repositories

Value proposition: “A new open platform for distributing/monetizing code-based sound works”.

Punchlines for authors:

- Be part of the **first public database of code-based sound works**.
- **Blockchain based authorship**: Version your works publicly and collectively while preserving authorship.
- **Register your works** in a decentralized and sustainable platform.
- **Distribute and monetize your patch**: get paid automatically when your repository is used by others.
- **Performer in the loop**: Enter into a synergistic relationship with your performers.
- **Community building**, knowledge sharing, social interaction, groupware, advertisement, promotion, reputation.

Punchlines for users:

- **Get inspired and learn** from the repositories of others.
- **A unique public works repository** for contemporary musicology.
- **Artist in the loop**: Enter into a synergistic relationship with the authors.
- **Community building**, knowledge sharing, social interaction, groupware, advertisement, promotion.
- **Sponsor the authors** indirectly by purchasing repositories from them.

6.1.1.5 Scenario 2.3 - Creation and use of works / private spaces

Value proposition: “A web 3 community for supporting experimental music/sound creation”

Punchlines for authors:

- **Grant exclusive access to your artwork** and the tools you develop: Generative works. Generative process. Algorithmic composition.; VR installation, ephemeral links/artworks, web art; web services such generative web stream/radio.
- **Create your virtual private showroom** to interact with your fans: Promoting space: Artistic promotion, showroom; Service/event promotion; Festival Boot: Professional networking; Public sponsoring exposure.
- **Manage your fan store**: Grant access to goodies, derived products, commercial discounts.
- **Create a village center** for your creative community.
- **Register your works** in a decentralized and sustainable platform.
- **Monetize your works**: get paid automatically when your works is used by others.
- **Fans in the loop**: Enter into a synergistic relationship with your fans.
- **Community building**, knowledge sharing, social interaction, groupware, advertisement, promotion, reputation.

Punchlines for users:

- **Get inspired and learn** from the works of others.
- **Artist in the loop**: Enter into a synergistic relationship with the authors.
- **Community building**, knowledge sharing, social interaction, groupware, advertisement, promotion.
- **Sponsor the authors** indirectly by purchasing works from them.

- **Become a digital art collector.**

6.1.1.6 Scenarios 3.1 and 3.2 - Repository/Component creator and user

Value proposition:

- “Focus on alternative economic models for open source projects”.
- “Get access to /contribute to/ support latest emerging technologies for creatives”.
- “Connecting NFT’s to physical work such as OS hardware, crafts, etc.”.

Punchlines:

- DAFNE+ aims to makes blockchain technology accessible for designers and makers.
- Create, co-create, and showcase your work with ease.
- Join the DAFNE+ community and discover new forms of creation, distribution, and monetization for your work.
- Connect with other designers and makers on DAFNE+ and explore new business models for your designs.
- DAFNE+ enables you to monetize your open source projects in a fair and decentralized way.
- Embrace a new economic paradigm where creators and users are part of the same community and benefit together.
- Collaborate, share, and learn from a network of like-minded creatives.
- Join a community of designers and makers to find new opportunities, collaborations, and support.
- Collaborate with fellow creators and makers to create a new, fairer ecosystem for digital content with DAFNE+ DAOs.

6.1.2 At Project level (UPM)

The promotion of DAFNE+ project is described in *D7.1 Dissemination, Communication and Agile Stakeholders management plan*. The dissemination efforts will focus on sharing project results, including fundamental knowledge, methodologies, and technologies developed during the project. The aim is to enhance the use of these outcomes for the benefit of the target audience. Additionally, knowledge transfer activities will be conducted to enable others to adopt and utilize the project results.

In DAFNE+ we are using a mix of online and offline channels to ensure effective dissemination and engagement with stakeholders. The combination of these channels will allow for targeted and widespread communication, keeping all interested parties informed and involved throughout the project.

We can find the activities that are envisioned in Section 3 of the above-mentioned document. Nevertheless, we are using an agile stakeholder’s management framework that runs in 6 months sprints. In the 4th phase of each sprint we apply the lessons learned to adapt the general plan.

We will focus our promotion on the online channels:

- **Email:** DAFNE+ will have a mail list where people can opt-it to receive our newsletter.
- **Social media:** Platforms such as Twitter (<https://twitter.com/DAFNEplus>), LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/dafneplus>), and YouTube will be used to share updates and information about the DAFNE+ project with external stakeholders.
- **Discord:** we have setup a Discord channel where our users can interact between them.

We have scheduled two competition events for content creators, which will take place on M28 and M30 respectively. The purpose of these events is to provide creators with the opportunity to interact with the

DAFNE+ platform and provide feedback. Participants will be grouped into creators teams and given the chance to experiment with DAFNE+ tools, resources, and the dedicated environment. The competition will be conducted in a friendly atmosphere.

Overall, the dissemination strategy of DAFNE+ seeks to effectively communicate the project's achievements, engage stakeholders, transfer knowledge, and enable the widespread utilization of project results for the benefit of the target audience and the project's long-term sustainability.

6.1.3 Use-case 1

In this use case, we have identified two distinct communities that will require different promotion strategies. The challenge lies in effectively reaching each community's audience, given their different profiles. To tackle this challenge, we plan to implement two separate promotion strategies that align with the overall project strategy.

We will begin by identifying the different profiles of ambassadors that are most suitable for each community. Once we have identified the profiles, we will provide the ambassadors with the necessary training to become effective advocates for our platform. The training will include workshops that cover the use and values of the DAFNE+ platform, as well as communication strategies that are tailored to the specific community.

In addition to training our ambassadors, we will also engage in social media through the profiles of the project. These communications will be designed to resonate with each community's unique values and interests, and will feature ambassadors as key influencers and advocates. By combining social media with ambassador advocacy, we hope to create a powerful and effective promotion strategy that will engage and inspire both communities to join the DAFNE+ platform.

Cultural heritage has been recognized as an essential component of the tourism industry. It serves as a way to attract visitors to destinations that offer unique cultural experiences. In this regard, it is not surprising to see advocates of cultural heritage preservation and promotion attending various tourism events. These advocates aim to raise awareness about the significance of cultural heritage in tourism and the need to preserve it for future generations.

The consortium partners of DAFNE+ shares this vision. They come from countries that are considered top destinations for cultural tourism, including France, Greece, and Spain. These countries are proud of their cultural heritage, and they are committed to promoting it to the world. As such, the partners of DAFNE+ recognize the importance of preserving cultural heritage and maximizing its potential for the tourism industry.

To achieve this goal, the consortium will identify key events that attract tourists interested in cultural heritage. They will promote DAFNE+ among attendees by relying on ambassadors of the platform. These ambassadors will be experts in cultural heritage and will provide valuable insights into the platform's features and benefits. By doing so, the consortium hopes to attract more users to the platform and contribute to the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage in tourism.

6.1.4 Use-case 2

The strategy for promoting the DAFNE+ platform by IRCAM for Use-case 2 is centrifugal, with the aim of reaching its various circles of influence through graduated efforts.

At its heart, IRCAM aims to integrate use of the platform as an evolution of its internal operations. Components from its research department will become accessible via DAFNE+. Hosted students as part of their composition or design curricula will be proposed to publish their works on the platform. A private space

on the platform will be allocated to composers in research or production to enable direct connection with their audience. Specific artistic production projects will be selected to promote NFT-based sponsoring. These activities will be relayed by IRCAM's corporate Communication Service in synergy with UPM.

Beyond the circle of IRCAM collaborators, the IRCAM Forum community will be also widely solicited. An international community of users of IRCAM technologies, the IRCAM Forum brings together artists, creators, teachers, researchers, performers, students and sound professionals. Here, they can discover the latest musical applications and appropriate new sound technologies designed by IRCAM laboratories or other members, interact with the community, share activities and events, collaborate on joint projects, or simply ask questions to a network of professionals with over 40,000 members worldwide. Thanks to the sharing of technological bricks between the two platforms, the user experience is easy to switch from one platform to the other, so that users of the IRCAM Forum can easily get to grips with the DAFNE+ platform.

Experts and recognized actors in several fields (algorithmic composition, electronic music, sound design) will be enrolled as ambassadors for the DAFNE+ platform. These ambassadors will have a dissemination role in their respective communities. A pool of beta-testers will also be assembled at the platform's launch.

In order to accelerate the adoption of the platform by new users, the introduction of two prizes is envisaged. These two new prizes will be awarded at the festive event to mark the 30th anniversary of the IRCAM Forum, which will take place in Paris from March 19 to 22, 2024, and will propose the applicants to publish their works on the DAFNE+ platform. This date corresponds to the start of the evaluation of the first circle of DAFNE+ pilots and is appropriate for a setting a first public milestone after the platform launch. In this indirect way, the community phished by the prize will be confronted with the use of the platform, which will also offer them the opportunity to make the submission public in order to win NFTs. The two prizes envisaged are:

- Generative music prize.
- Multichannel work prize

Since attributing financial counterparts to third parties is not a priori foreseen in the DAFNE+ funding framework, the launch of the calls will depend on additional fundings in the framework of IRCAM activities, in particular in relation to industrial partners and with the help of ambassadors. If confirmed, the call for prize will take place during the 2023/2024 winter semester.

Several dissemination and support actions are planned accordingly. Among these, incentives to register on the DAFNE+ platform, and then to participate in the March event, will be relayed on the monthly bilingual (French and English) newsletters of the IRCAM Forum, which has around 3000 recipients. A webinar is planned to coincide with the platform's release, to help users get to grips with it. A recording of the webinar will be used to produce an online tutorial. A DAFNE+ workshop is also planned as part of the IRCAM Forum workshops, possibly in a joint event under discussion with other French institutions.

A publication is also planned for the 10th International Conference on Digital Libraries for Musicology (DLfM 2023), to be held on November 10, 2023.

These actions planned for the first 9 months of the pilots and will be completed by others.

6.1.5 Use-case 3

Use-case 3, led by IAAC, aims to effectively promote and communicate DAFNE+ to the interconnected communities of the Distributed Design Platform and Fab Lab Barcelona. These communities include over 1600 innovative creators in various fields such as making, art, and design and as part of the global Fab Lab

Network, more than 35,000 users worldwide. By using the extensive network of the Distributed Design and Fab Lab Barcelona, Use-case 3 aims to engage with creative individuals, educators, academics, art collectors, art curators, researchers, and managers in these communities and achieve through a comprehensive set of initiatives that cover online promotion, on-site events, and global activities. The focus of these initiatives is to enhance capacity building related to DAFNE+ platform's key topics and facilitate collaborations among partners, while also creating opportunities aligned with the project's objectives. The planned activities include:

Online promotion/ communication:

The main focus of online promotion and communication activities has been determined based on the digital reach of the Distributed Design Platform. In the year 2022/2023, the platform's website and blog posts reached over 60,000 people, the newsletter reached over 1,300 people, and more than 27.000 accounts on Social Media. The EU-funded project section mentions the Distributed Design Platform on the Fab Lab Barcelona website with approximately 34,000 visitors annually.

- Blog post for Distributed Design Platform and Fab Lab Barcelona website: A blog post will be created to showcase the project objectives and highlight the potentials for creatives. This post will be published on both the Distributed Design Platform and Fab Lab Barcelona websites (approximately 34,000 visitors annually).
- Additional social media posts on Distributed Design Platform and Fab Lab Barcelona channels (Instagram, LinkedIn etc.) to reach a wider audience (Distributed Design Platform reaches more than 27.000 accounts through the Social Media).
- A podcast series called "[Future Talks](#)" has been successfully launched by Fab Lab Barcelona. This series of episodes offers a platform to host experts from the platform's partners and members of the Distributed Design Platform. This podcast series focus on discussing emergent futures and will serve as a platform to explore relevant topics related to the project. "Future Talks" contributes to the promotion and dissemination of knowledge within the project's goals.

On-Site Events

- Cluster2 Event at DesignHUB: From 11th to 13th of July, a Cluster2 Event will be organized at DHUB by by the [Spanish Foundation of Science and Technology](#) (FECYT) This event will provide a direct connection to the local community and creative talents, allowing for meaningful engagement and interactions. Furthermore, there are more than 300 people from cultural and creative organisation invited to join the three day event in Barcelona. To collectively share their visions about the intersections of art and science during curated talks, workshops and exchanged.
- Maker Faire held in Vienna, Lisbon, and Milan (to be confirmed). These events are renowned platforms for showcasing innovative projects and will help gather attention and support for the Distributed Design Platform members.
- Possible other dissemination and communication activities such as the [Life Changing Design by the International Association of Societies of Design Research Conference](#) and the [Impact Festival Frankfurt](#) are to be further explored.

Global Activities

- Creative video capsules: Consortium members and guest speakers will be invited to collaborate and host creative video capsules. These videos will highlight the project's key topics, features, innovations aspects, and impact. They will be shared through various channels to reach a global audience and generate interest in the Distributed Design Platform.

The promotion/communication strategy will primarily focus on capacity building in line with the Distributed Design Platform and Fab Lab Barcelona values. By highlighting the project's objectives, opportunities, and engaging with various communities and events, the aim is to strengthen the platform's presence and foster collaborations worldwide.

6.2 User support and community management

6.2.1 At Project level

DAFNE+ platform will include a FAQ module which includes both text and video content to address the most frequently asked questions. The module is accessible to all users and serves as the first layer of support. However, in case a user has a question that is not answered by the FAQ module, there is a form available on the project's website that can be filled out to submit any question. The form is designed to be user-friendly and simple to use. Once a question is submitted, UPM will either provide an answer to the question or redirect the inquiry to the appropriate partner. This process ensures that every user's question is addressed and that they receive the support they need to use the DAFNE+ platform effectively.

We have defined the role of ambassadors, this ambassador is an early-adopter within the communities that are tackled by the use cases. This ambassador must be a trustworthy creator in that will help the use cases to grow and spread the information of DAFNE+ platform.

To facilitate their efforts, a comprehensive ambassador kit is being developed, comprising all the necessary information for effective collaboration with the DAFNE+ platform. Additionally, promotional materials tailored to the ambassadors' needs will be provided, empowering them to amplify their outreach within their respective social media communities.

Since the NFT and cryptocurrency communities frequently engage in conversation over Discord, we have set up a server to engage with them in their natural space. We believe that it is important to create a welcoming environment for these communities to connect and share their interests with like-minded individuals. To accomplish this, we will create a channel for each use case so that members can join discussions, ask questions, and share their thoughts on various topics. Through these channels, we hope to build a community where individuals can learn from each other, discover new opportunities, and stay up-to-date on the latest news on DAFNE+.

6.2.2 Use-case 1

Throughout the testing phase of the DAFNE+ Platform, we will prioritize the satisfaction and support of our users by diligently addressing their informational requirements. In this regard, we will augment the existing platform-level Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) section by incorporating the specific queries arising from our use case. Moreover, we will actively engage with our user community through the Discord channel, fostering and encouraging meaningful discussions that can contribute to an enhanced user experience. By actively participating in these discussions, we aim to provide prompt assistance, gather valuable feedback, and foster a collaborative environment conducive to the refinement and optimization of the DAFNE+ Platform.

6.2.3 Use-case 2

In the creation of a platform, user support and community management are crucial aspects to ensure the success and engagement of users. For Use-case 2, IRCAM is offering the community the benefit of its Forum expertise. A public discussion thread on DAFNE+ in IRCAM's Forum will enable to motivate Forum members, answer questions and share experiences. IRCAM will also contribute to DAFNE+'s FAQ specific to its community. Webinars will accompany the launch of the platform. These will be captured and used to produce video tutorials. Notifications on platform activity will be also a useful source of information for putting forward interesting news to the community.

6.2.4 Use-case 3

The task of "User support and community management" includes capacity-building activities for the Distributed Design Platform such as a focus group for testing the BETA version of the platform, workshops with the students from the Master in Design for Emergent Futures students, workshops with the local creative community of Poblenou in Barcelona (Spain) during the @Poblenou Open Day and collaborations with Espacio Open, and connecting with Distributed Design Platform's members for activities in the framework of Distributed Design Platform yearly program.

To ensure broad participation and engagement, the following open calls will be conducted:

- **Ambassadors:** An open call will be launched to choose Ambassadors who will have the opportunity to test the beta version of the platform, and actively participate in workshops and other relevant activities.
- An open invitation will be extended to experts, creatives and enthusiasts of the IAAC community, inviting them to take part in the workshops. This inclusive approach aims to encourage a diverse range of perspectives and contributions to the platform testing phase.

These activities aim to gather feedback, share knowledge, empower its users by actively involving the global and local community in the ongoing platform's development.

6.3 Monitoring and evaluation

The project aims to perform monitoring and evaluation activities, both to assess the project's success and progress using KPIs defined in the GA, as well as with Use Case metrics, described in detail in the two following subsections. Following those subsections, we describe the different types of means of evaluation, the methodology to be used and the proposed timeline for the first round of evaluation with the end users.

6.3.1 Introduction

The evaluation of the DAFNE+ platform will focus on diverse aspects covering not only technical but also usability/acceptability aspects as well as metrics that will allow us to assess the innovation potential and the level of motivation for engagement with culture. The evaluation will be done with the end users, after first technical validation in the lab. As the 1st version of the platform will integrate a sub-set of the functionalities with this subset including the most desired features, the evaluation of this version will also focus on collecting feedback for specific aspects of the platform. This is also necessary as recruiting end users and having them evaluating the platform is a process that needs proper handling to avoid overwhelming them so that they keep engaged and continue helping us in refining our platform. This is completely in line with the best practices for innovative solutions where focusing on the evaluation of a few KPIs is the key for a successful solution development and potential to the market. The use-case partners will be involved in this process of involvement of users of their communities along the various evaluation means including user surveys, expert surveys, and focus groups.

6.3.2 Means of evaluation

To measure both the GA KPIs and the Use case Metrics we consider metrics of different nature (quantitative and qualitative), and that will be collected using a diversity of means:

- **Platform and tool metrics:** Platform and tool metrics will be collected by the software and collected using a shared metrics platform (an instance of the open source Matomo software). A specific category of these type of metrics are conversion metrics, that will help the project build a funnel model to understand where the users are struggling to engage with the proposal, or how easy it is for them to jump to the next level of engagement or expertise.
- **Demos:** Demos where users access and use the tools of the project are also a key tool to measure the project's progress and success. In these demos, users from different communities will give their feedback. Furthermore, usability and design insights can be obtained from these experiments through observation of the users' behavior with the tools.
- **User surveys:** User surveys will provide qualitative information about the user's perception about the platform and tools. This information will often be collected in the form of likert scale answers.
- **Expert's surveys:** Expert's feedback is also of great interest to measure aspects such as the innovation of the project and other factors that regular users might not be able to answer. These surveys will also collect the answers using mainly likert scale questions.
- **Social network analysis:** From the metrics directly collected by the platform and tools, one of the most interesting are those that represent interactions and relationships between users. These interactions can help us get a picture of the inequalities within the network, success factors for artists and creators, or how clusters and groups of users are created. These metrics will be collected and explored to inform the development of the platform.

6.3.3 Methodology and timeline

These metrics will be measured within the calendar defined in the framework of WP5 to measure and compare the initial plans and expectations with the final outcome through different stages:

- **Stage 1:** Evaluation of the system before starting the pilots (M16).
- **Stage 2:** Mid-term evaluation, with the use cases taking place (M26).
- **Stage 3:** Final evaluation, with the use cases finished (M36).

The KPIs defined in the GA that are relevant to be measured during the 1st stage of the pilot are included in the following table along with the means that are considered more suitable to be used. Although this list has been prepared up to M12, adjustments and finetuning may happen even at the time of running the pilots, to better fit the user needs. Based on this table of KPIs, we have defined the questionnaires that will be distributed during the pilots so that we reach a quantitative assessment, one to be completed by users and one by experts. These questionnaires appears in the sequel.

In addition to collect a wide diversity of metrics, the project will select the most important metrics to understand the success and progress of the platform. This follows best practices in product design and "Lean Design" methodologies, where product designers and startups are encouraged to find just one key metric to drive their efforts. These metrics, often called Key Performance Indicators or KPIs should be carefully crafted in order to avoid vanity metrics, such as number of visits to the platform without considering how many actually return and keep interacting in the platform. A prioritization of the most relevant KPIs will be regularly discussed and updated.

It is important to emphasize that although the metrics identified during the workshops have been chosen for use in a particular use case, they are not intended to be exclusive. The use of these metrics could potentially be beneficial for other use cases within DAFNE+ and thus eventually be subject to generalization.

KPI	Evaluation Means
Economical: increase in possibilities for media creators and composers to control own communities without external interferences > 30%	User survey
Integrity and transparency: 100% of information always available on the blockchain and attributable to the owner	Platform
Privacy: GDPR fully compliant and 100% of instances of personal data correctly managed by the system.	Platform
At least one modular platform able to interrelate features extracted from the network patterns	Platform
Time to create NFTs for creators and artists: reduction of 80% from using separate and non-automated tools.	User Survey
Usage of provided production modules/ workflows > 1 per user in the pilots	Platform
Number of items shared by community users > 1 per user	Platform
Statistic of re-use of community-shared items > 2 per user	Platform
Community members generating tokens daily >2%	Platform
Community members active weekly >15%	Platform
Community members active monthly >25%	Platform
At least 200 participants in the pilots	Platform
80%+ satisfaction rate	User Survey
At least 10 non cultural industries interested in the pilots' results.	Experts' survey
Use Case 1: At least 100 final users will be selected	Platform
Use Case 2: At least 50 final users will be selected	Platform
Use Case 3: At least 50 final users will be selected	Platform
Short term: Increase in innovation capabilities of the CCI workers involved in the project >15%	User Survey

Short term: New workflows defined and enabled by DAFNE+ >3	Experts' survey
Medium term: New business models defined and supported by DAFNE+ platform > 4	Project result
Medium term: Decrease in time to market due to the exploitation of DAFNE+ tools >20% (judged by external to the consortium people engaged in workshops)	Experts' survey
Short term: Number of sectors for which DAFNE+ application has been investigated and evaluated with experts > 3	Project result
Short term: Credibility of the study (assessed by external experts) > 8 (10 points scale)	Experts' survey
Medium Term: Increase in the innovation potential of additional sectors as estimated by external experts > 15%	Experts' survey
Short term: Easiness to use DAFNE+ content creation tools > 4 (In 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey
Short term: Easiness to use DAFNE+ NFT application of content distribution > 4 (In 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey
Medium term: Intention to use DAFNE+ tools to embrace with CCI > 4 (In 5 points Likert scale)	User Survey
Short term: Satisfaction from the DAFNE+ distribution model in DAFNE+ sectors >4 (5 points Likert scale)	User Survey
Medium term: Satisfaction from the DAFNE+ distribution model in other sectors >4 (5 points Likert scale)	User Survey
Short term: Document providing lessons learnt and recommendations for strengthening the competitiveness of EU CCI sector based on DAFNE+ offerings/tools/paradigm	Project result

Table 1 KPIs from the GA that will be assessed in the pilots and the relevant means for producing them.

Question	Answer type	KPI group	Project KPI we aim to quantify
How satisfied are you from the DAFNE+ platform?	Radar from 0% to 100%		80%+ satisfaction rate

How easy to use are DAFNE+ content creation tools?	5-point likert scale	User satisfaction and easiness of use	Short term: Easiness to use DAFNE+ content creation tools > 4 (In 5 points Likert scale)
How easy to use is DAFNE+ NFT application?	5-point likert scale		Short term: Easiness to use DAFNE+ NFT application of content distribution > 4 (In 5 points Likert scale)
DAFNE+ allows creators and artists to easily create NFTs. How easily is this compared to using separate non-automated tools?	Radar from 0% to 100%		Time to create NFTs for creators and artists: reduction of 80% from using separate and non-automated tools.
Are you satisfied from the DAFNE+ revenue distribution model?	5-point likert scale		Short term: Satisfaction from the DAFNE+ distribution model in DAFNE+ sectors >4 (5 points Likert scale)
How likely is for you to use DAFNE+ tools in the future?	5-point likert scale		Medium term: Intention to use DAFNE+ tools to embrace with CCI > 4 (In 5 points Likert scale)
If you consider that DAFNE+ platform offers you innovation capabilities, how much these capabilities increase?	Radar from 0% to 100%	Business creation capabilities	Short term: Increase in innovation capabilities of the CCI workers involved in the project >15%
The creation of communities of media creators and composers is anticipated to lead to economical increase. How high would you expect this to be?	Radar from 0% to 100%		Economical: increase in possibilities for media creators and composers to control own communities without external interferences > 30%

Table 2 Questionnaire to be used in the pilots with the end users

Question	Answer type	KPI group	Project KPI we aim to quantify
Apart from the workflows that you have been just presented to you, can you think of additional ones that would create added value?	Free text	DAFNE+ business value in the	Short term: New workflows defined and enabled by DAFNE+ >3

DAFNE+ aspires to decrease the time to market due to the exploitation of DANFE+ tools. Estimate this decrease based on your experience.	Radar button from 0% to 80%	cultural sector	Medium term: Decrease in time to market due to the exploitation of DAFNE+ tools >20% (judged by external to the consortium people engaged in workshops)
Do you consider that NFT-based marketplaces would be of interest to other industries (apart from culture)?	Yes/No/Maybe	Replication potential	At least 10 non cultural industries interested in the pilots' results.
If you answered yes in the previous question, please name the relevant industries	Free text		
The innovation potential of the above named industries would then be expected to increase. In which proportion?	Radar button from 0% to 80%		Medium Term: Increase in the innovation potential of additional sectors as estimated by external experts > 15%
Assuming that you consider that the revenue distribution models supported by DAFNE+ are appropriate for other sectors, how much satisfying/appropriate do you consider them to be?	5-point likert scale		Medium term: Satisfaction from the DAFNE+ distribution model in other sectors >4 (5 points Likert scale)
You were presented the study of DAFNE+ consortium on the replication of its approach to other industries. How credible do you consider this study?	10-point likert scale		Short term: Credibility of the study (assessed by external experts) > 8 (10 points scale)

Table 3 Questionnaire to be used in the pilots with the experts

6.3.4 Use Case Metrics

Additionally, within the DAFNE+ use case development task, we have conducted a collaborative workshop with representatives from each use case to select specific metrics within each of the following categories:

1. **User acceptance metrics:** measuring how users perceive the problem and the solution we are providing to solve their needs:
 - a. Problem relevance
 - b. Solution relevance
 - c. Solution Performance
2. **Usability metrics:** measure how easy and enjoyable it is to use the tools and the platform.
3. **Motivation and engagement metrics:** measuring how attractive the proposal is for our target audience, and how committed and engaged the users are with the tools and the platform.

The use case representatives actively participated, offering valuable insights based on their unique requirements and objectives. Their direct involvement ensured that the chosen metrics truly reflected the

needs and priorities of each use case, leveraging their domain expertise. This approach resulted in a well-rounded set of metrics that accurately captured the different aspects to be measured in each use case.

Following the collaborative workshop, the selected metrics were operationalized to effectively track and evaluate the progress of each use case. This involved translating the identified metrics into practical measurement systems, identifying both the means of evaluation and potential items or tools to be used.

These metrics are summarized in the following tables.

6.3.4.1 User acceptance metrics

6.3.4.1.1 Problem relevance metrics

Metric	Evaluation Means
Sustainable Livelihood Percentage: proportion of individuals able to sustain their livelihood through profits generated from open source projects	User Survey
Perceived Economic Inequality: Average perception of individuals within different demographic groups regarding economic profit inequalities	User Survey
Percentage of users that do not understand the platform rules	User Survey
Percentage of revenue that goes to creators	Platform
Proportion of individuals belonging to marginalized communities	User survey
Average amount of carbon dioxide equivalent emissions generated during the process of creating and distributing an NFT	User survey
Average perceived solution transparency	User survey

Table 4 Problem relevance metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them

6.3.4.1.2 Solution relevance metrics

Metric	Evaluation Means
Average perceived sustainability of the solution	User Survey
Overall perception of empowerment among creators	User Survey
Perceived innovation of the solution	User Survey
Average user empowerment perception	User Survey
Percentage of users perceiving the platform as fair in ecological impact, revenue distribution and transparency	User Survey
Level of adoption of the solution by the users	Platform
Extent to which the solution promotes collaboration and partnerships between different stakeholders	Platform

Table 5 Solution relevance metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them

6.3.4.1.3 Solution performance metrics

Metric	Evaluation Means
User satisfaction with the solution	User Survey
Average social media interactions per artwork and artist	Platform / Social Media
Average number of unique interactions per artwork	Platform
Average revenue per piece of art	Platform

Number of new and different forms of artwork created through DAFNE+	Platform
Cost-effectiveness of the solution in terms of the resources required to implement and maintain it	User survey
Number of transactions enabled by the platform	Platform
Users' satisfaction regarding the platform performance	User survey
Cost-effectiveness of the solution in terms of the resources required to implement and maintain it	User survey

Table 6 Solution performance metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them

6.3.4.2 Usability metrics

Metric	Evaluation Means
Average time to learn how to use the platform	Platform
Proportion of users who assess the system usability as satisfactory	User Survey
Task completion rate of creating/purchasing a NFT	Platform
Perceived ease with which users can complete tasks or achieve goals	Platform
Likelihood of users to recommend the platform	User survey
Proportion of users who assess the usability of the DAFNE+ system as satisfactory based on their responses to the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire	User survey
Average amount of time it takes for creators to produce a single Non-Fungible Token (NFT) within the platform	Platform

Table 7 Usability metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them

6.3.4.3 Motivation and engagement metrics

Metric	Evaluation Means
Abandonment rate: percentage of users who leave the funnel before completing a specific action	Platform
Referral rate: percentage of users referred by DAFNE+ users	Platform
Community Care Index: level of care and support experienced by users within the platform	User Survey
Average number of connections, interactions or collaborations established between users	Platform
Average easiness and pleasing nature of transactions	User Survey
Number of NFTs purchased through the platform	Platform
Number of derivative works generated through the platform	Platform
Number of referrals	Platform
Rate of artists stopping using the platform	Platform
Rate of artists with at least one sale out of the total number of artists who produced any NFTs	Platform

Table 8 Motivation and engagement metrics that will be assessed and the relevant means for producing them

It is important to emphasize that although the metrics identified during the workshops have been chosen for use in a particular use case, they are not intended to be exclusive. The use of these metrics could potentially be beneficial for other use cases within DAFNE+ and thus eventually be subject to generalization.

7 Conclusions

The specification of use-cases resulting from a process carried out during the first year of the DAFNE+ project have been presented, through a common formalism and structure. It exhibits strong similarities between the 3 use-cases, although addressing very different communities, which favors a common way of managing them in the DAFNE+ platform and activities. This specification prepares the implementation of the first phase use-case pilots that will be followed by a new cycle of feedback, evaluation and specification.

